

Twenty Years of Personality Computing: Threats, Challenges and Future Directions

FABIO CELLI, Research & Development, Maggioli SpA, Santarcangelo di Romagna, Italy and Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Italy

ALEKSANDAR KARTELJ, Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

MILJAN ĐORĐEVIĆ, School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

DERWIN SUHARTONO, School of Computer Science, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia

VLADIMIR FILIPOVIĆ, Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

VELJKO MILUTINOVIĆ, School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

GEORGIOS SPATHOULAS, Department of Information Security and Communication Technology, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Gjøvik, Norway

ALESSANDRO VINCIARELLI, School of Computing Science, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

MICHAL KOSINSKI, Graduate School of Business, Stanford University, Stanford, United States

BRUNO LEPRI, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Italy

Personality Computing is a field at the intersection of Personality Psychology and Computer Science. Started in 2005, research in the field utilizes computational methods to understand and predict human personality traits. The expansion of the field has been very rapid and, by analyzing digital footprints (text, images, social media, etc.), it helped to develop systems that recognize and even replicate human personality. While offering promising applications in talent recruiting, marketing and healthcare, the ethical implications of Personality Computing are significant. Concerns include data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the potential for manipulation by personality-aware Artificial Intelligence. This article provides an overview of the field, explores key methodologies, discusses the challenges and threats, and outlines potential future directions for responsible development and deployment of Personality Computing technologies.

This research was supported by the European Commission, grant 101120657: European Lighthouse to Manifest Trustworthy and Green AI—ENFIELD.

Authors' Contact Information: Fabio Celli (corresponding author), Research & Development, Maggioli SpA, Santarcangelo di Romagna, Italy and Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Trentino-Alto Adige, Italy; e-mail: fabio.celli.phd@gmail.com; Aleksandar Kartelj, Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia; e-mail: aleksandar.kartelj@gmail.com; Mijan Đorđević, School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia; e-mail: miljandv@gmail.com; Derwin Suhartono, School of Computer Science, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia; e-mail: dsuhartono@binus.edu; Vladimir Filipović, Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia; e-mail: vladaf@math.rs; Veljko Milutinović, School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia; e-mail: veljko.milutinovic@fon.bg.ac.rs; Georgios Spathoulas, Department of Information Security and Communication Technology, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Gjøvik, Oppland, Norway; e-mail: georgios.spathoulas@ntnu.no; Alessandro Vinciarelli, School of Computing Science, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, Glasgow, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland; e-mail: Alessandro.Vinciarelli@glasgow.ac.uk; Michal Kosinski, Graduate School of Business, Stanford University, Stanford, California, United States; e-mail: michalk@stanford.edu; Bruno Lepri, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Trentino-Alto Adige, Italy; e-mail: lepri@fbk.eu.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

© 2026 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).

ACM 0360-0300/2026/04-ART293

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3806009>

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Clustering and classification**; *Personalization*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Information extraction*; *Supervised learning by classification*; • **Human-centered computing** → *Social tagging*; • **Security and privacy** → *Social aspects of security and privacy*;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Personality computing, personality recognition, personality perception, personality synthesis

ACM Reference Format:

Fabio Celli, Aleksandar Kartelj, Miljan Đorđević, Derwin Suhartono, Vladimir Filipović, Veljiko Milutinović, Georgios Spathoulas, Alessandro Vinciarelli, Michal Kosinski, and Bruno Lepri. 2026. Twenty Years of Personality Computing: Threats, Challenges and Future Directions. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 58, 11, Article 293 (April 2026), 37 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3806009>

1 Introduction

Personality Computing is a research field started in 2005 that uses computational methods to understand and predict human personality. There are many digital footprints conveying information that computational models can decode and use in various ways to model behavior and interact with humans. These include text [176, 178, 179], images [87, 248, 249], video and audio tracks [132, 194, 222, 272], social media posts and preferences [158, 160, 246], credit card transactions [100, 266], mobile phone communication logs [53, 65, 196, 254], experience sampling apps [182], and physiological data [77]. The basis for training Personality Computing models comes from Personality Psychology [234], primarily using questionnaires to assess and quantify personality traits [37, 62]. The availability of data that combine digital footprints and scores from personality assessments allowed the development of systems that recognize human personality exploiting sophisticated computational techniques, including **Natural Language Processing (NLP)**, **Computer Vision (CV)**, **Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)**, **Deep Learning (DL)**, and **Social Network Analysis (SNA)**. Systems for Personality Computing have been applied in different domains, both at population (i.e., targeted marketing [46, 244], recommendation systems [68]) and individual level (i.e., mental health detection [298], job performance [15, 156], human-computer interaction [22, 23]).

Crucially, these algorithms were employed in numerous applications that pose serious threats to societal integrity, such as digital mass persuasion on voters in various elections [243, 295], surveillance and social scoring systems that integrate personality, raising serious concerns about the ethical use of Personality Computing. As a result, the data protection regulations (e.g., the European Union General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR¹) and the legislation on Artificial Intelligence (e.g., the European Union AI Act²) often limit Personality Computing. There are restrictions on the types of data that can be collected, rules prohibiting uses that could be discriminatory or harmful, and laws that require systems to be transparent about how personality inferences are made (i.e., explanations for automated decisions involving personality). Recent advancements in **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** have led to **Large Language Models (LLMs)**, which are able to detect and replicate human personality during interactions and role-playing tasks [121, 125, 126, 135, 136, 219, 275, 276], potentially reaching a high level of intimacy between AI systems and humans. This might yield to scenarios where AI systems can manipulate humans to engineer large scale social functions, such as voting and spending, with a disruptive impact on human societies [116]. This is why a survey of this field is essential to identify challenges and explore ways to mitigate the negative social impacts of Personality Computing.

¹<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

²<https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

The objective of this article is to systematically examine the development of Personality Computing over the past two decades, with a focus on its methods, applications, ethical challenges, and future research directions. It is structured as follows: first we introduce the definition of personality traits and the notion of personality states. In Section 2, we take an overview of the field, its history, benchmarks and the **State-of-the-Art (SotA)**. In Section 3, we discuss methods and techniques to build Personality Computing systems with different types of data sources, from text to multimedia and mobile phone traces [180]. Finally, after introducing ethical issues (Section 3.5), we draw our conclusions in Section 4, where we discuss threats and challenges in Personality Computing, and outline possible future directions to mitigate negative effects for societies. The novelty of our article with respect to previous work is to present a comprehensive overview about Personality Computing to a computer science readership, adding the emergent approaches based on (LLMs and discussing potential threats posed by these systems. We believe that this article could be a valuable resource for future generations of researchers in Personality Computing to develop trustworthy AI agents.

2 Background, History, and Resources

2.1 What is Personality?

Personality is a complex system of individual characteristics that strongly affects a person's thoughts, emotions, and behavior in any given situation. It is visible in both digital and real-world interactions, and it significantly shapes one's self-image, expectations, values, and attitudes [140]. Personality Psychology is a branch of psychology that aims at describing, explaining, and understanding the functioning of personality by examining both between-person differences and within-person dynamics [234], providing frameworks for personality assessments [34, 140]. Research in Personality Psychology began one century ago and produced different methods for assessing personality (see Section 2.2). The availability of widely accepted personality assessment methods, both self-reported and observer-rated, facilitated the collection of data annotated with personality scores and labels, serving as a gold standard in Personality Computing research. Another important and more recent concept is the notion of "psychological states", sometimes referred to as "states of personality" or "personality states" [93, 94]. In psychology, states are momentary manifestations of dispositions shaped by the person and the situation, while traits summarize long-term regularities. Unlike personality traits, which are relatively stable and enduring characteristics, states are transient and influenced by the immediate context [59, 90, 94]. A person may typically be introverted (trait), but in a highly social and exciting environment where they feel at ease, they might exhibit extraverted behavior (state) without changing personality. States of personality provides a more nuanced understanding of human behavior by acknowledging the dynamic interplay between stable dispositions and situational influences. In particular, adaptation effects were observed for agreeable and emotionally stable people. Some suggested that individuals with these states might evoke similar states in others during interactions [9]. Another essential aspect of personality is how it is perceived. The Brunswik lens model provides a framework for understanding the process of interpersonal perception. This model defines the relationship between observable cues (distal cues) and the ultimate judgment or perception (proximal percept). It emphasizes the probabilistic nature of this relationship, acknowledging that cues are not perfectly reliable indicators. In personality research, the lens model helps explain how individuals infer personality traits from observable behaviors, and acknowledges that these inferences are based on probabilistic cues and that accuracy can vary. The model is used to show how subjective cognitive and emotional states can form from objective quantifiable behaviors [280].

2.2 Personality Models

There are several models and assessments to measure personality. In Personality Computing, the most used personality assessments are questionnaires, that can map a set of items to specific personality traits and facets. For example, the item “I am reserved” is correlated with introversion. Of course questionnaires have biases, for example, the “social desirability” bias [161]: people taking personality tests often try to present themselves in a certain way, which can skew the results. While no single technique completely eliminates bias from personality tests, there are methods to statistically control it, like Social Desirability Scales [64], randomized response, and Lie scoring [131].

Personality Computing adopted as main conceptual models the Big Five and the **Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)** [197]. The Big Five emerged from the lexical tradition of Personality Psychology [8, 105, 216]. An application of this framework is the **Five-Factor Model (FFM)**, defined and measured using instruments such as the NEO item inventories. There are also other models, such as **Dominance, Influence, Steadiness, and Conscientiousness (DISC)** [210], Hogan [120], and the **Short Dark Triad (SD3)** [142], but they are used in specific contexts and are not common in Personality Computing. The MBTI and DISC are popular but present well-documented validity issues [38] and should not be used in scientific work. The Big Five and FFM models independently arrived to very similar conclusions about personality traits [203, 214] and quantify personality into the following five traits:

- (1) Openness to experience – intellectual and insightful versus shallow and unimaginative.
- (2) Conscientiousness – self-disciplined and organized versus inefficient and careless.
- (3) Extraversion – sociable, assertive, and playful versus aloof, reserved and shy.
- (4) Agreeableness – friendly and cooperative versus antagonistic and faultfinding.
- (5) Neuroticism – confident and calm versus anxious and insecure.

The Big Five, sometimes referred to as OCEAN, is based on a lexical approach to personality measurement [104, 185] and has been shown to generally hold across different ages, genders, and cultural lines [139, 184]. Additional research has shown that different tests, languages, and analysis methods do not alter the validity of the model [69, 139, 183]. Such extensive research has led many psychologists to adopt the Big Five, and it is the most widely accepted model of personality in academia [215]. Although the evidence on cross-cultural validity is mixed [41], the Big Five has been replicated in a variety of different languages and cultures, such as Chinese [267] and Indian [173]. However, some researchers suggest that the Openness trait is unsupported in some Asian cultures like the Chinese, the Japanese and the Philippine, and that a different sixth factor is sometimes identified [35, 51]. In its six-factor extension, OCEAN becomes **Honesty-Humility, Emotionality, eXtraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Openness (HEXACO)**.

The MBTI is based on Carl Jung’s personality typology [144] and classifies profiles into 16 categories based on the combination of 4 binary traits:

- (1) extroversion/introversion – introverts reflect before they act, while extroverts act before they think;
- (2) sensing/intuition – sensing trust concrete information, while intuitive trust abstract and theoretical information;
- (3) thinking/feeling – feeling decide based on emotions, while thinking involve logic and reason in their decisions;
- (4) judging/perceiving – judging prefer structure in their lives, while perceiving like change.

Despite Personality Psychology literature consistently shows that there is no validity to it [38], MBTI is sometimes adopted by computer scientists for the availability of data annotated with this model, and for the fact that its categorical output, as opposed to scalar scores, facilitates the use of

classification algorithms [44]. However, future generations of researchers in Personality Computing should not use MBTI as ground truth.

2.3 History of Personality Computing

For many years researchers in Personality Psychology used small data samples with as few as tens or hundreds of subjects. Between the 1950s and the 1970s, part of the research was focused on personality measurement [84], the validity of personality tests [106] and its real-life applications [202]. Moreover there was also an increasing awareness that personality and language are connected [107, 109]. The many different personality assessment tests developed in more than 60 years (see Section 2.4), allowed researchers in the field of Personality Computing to collect large datasets annotated with personality scores and types (see Section 2.5 for details) for training computational models. The demonstration that personality can be computed from language dates back to 1999 [218], but the first automatic classification of personality from text appeared in 2005 [261]. In our opinion, this marked the beginning of Personality Computing as a new field of research at the intersection of psychology and computer science. At the beginning, in the field of NLP, personality scores were often turned into categories with mean or median split, and Personality Recognition was addressed as a multi-class classification task. Since then, Personality Computing has expanded from NLP, becoming a field of research that bridges the gap between Personality Psychology, Affective Computing, and AI. Systems in Personality Computing use computational techniques to analyze digital footprints, from text messages to multimedia and other sources of data, to solve three key problems [272]:

- (1) **Automatic Personality Recognition**, the task of predicting personality based on the persons' digital records like texts, pictures, audio, multimedia, mobile phone traces, social media likes, and so on.
- (2) **Automatic Personality Perception**, whose aim is at computationally understanding and evaluating how personality is perceived from humans and machines.
- (3) **Automatic Personality Synthesis**, the task to create and evaluate personalities for virtual characters like avatars and AI agents.

Figure 1, taken from [272], depicts the relationship between the Brunswik Lens and the three main problems addressed in Personality Computing.

The Stimulus (μ_S) is the underlying personality of an individual. Ecological Validity (P_{EV}) measures how accurately this personality is reflected in observable behaviors or distal cues (the digital footprints available in the environment, e.g., clothing choices or profile picture selection). Proximal Cues are the cues processed and interpreted by an observer; these are inherently filtered by the observer's own biases and perceptual frameworks. Consequently, Representation Validity (P_{RV}) measures how well the observer's internal representation of the cues matches the actual proximal cues, and it is distinct from Ecological Validity. Finally, Perceptual Judgment (μ_P) is the observer's ultimate conclusion or perception of the individual's personality, formed on the basis of this processed information. The model highlights challenges for Personality Computing. One is the ecological validity of the data used. Personality Recognition measures how well digital footprints (distal cues) can predict assessed personality, which is a proxy of individual's true personality (μ_S). Personality Synthesis aims at generating cues that observers interpret as intended trait levels, while Personality Perception should measure the relationship between distal cues, proximal cues (often unobserved), and perceptual judgments.

A Personality Computing system or AI performing these three tasks with high accuracy is potentially able to manipulate humans by understanding, simulating, and adapting to our personality. Traditional machine learning systems target broad, population-level personality models, which

Fig. 1. Relationship between the Brunswik Lens and tasks in Personality Computing. The picture is taken from [272].

serve as mere proxies and lack individual precision. In contrast, AI is capable of far more nuanced interactions, reaching a level of “artificial intimacy” that demands a deeper ethical response (see Section 3.5).

The field of Personality Computing has seen a rapid expansion around Personality Recognition in the first 10 years and a growing interest toward the other Personality Computing tasks in more recent years. To trace the genesis of Personality Computing, we retrieved from Scopus a citation network of the works cited in this article, and filtered works with in-degree ≥ 5 . The resulting graph (Figure 2) illustrates the foundational articles that merged psychology and computer science. We present them in a mix of chronological order and impact. The first influential article, Pennebaker J.W. et al. 1999 [218], created the first dataset (Essays) and the first resource (**Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count - LIWC**) for Personality Computing. Another influential article, Mehl M.R. et al. 2006 [186], started a line of research that observes how personality is shown and interpreted during normal, daily activities.

The foundation of Personality Computing began with Mairesse F. et al. (2007), who bridged psychology and computer science by using psycholinguistic features and machine learning to classify personality from text and audio. Though accuracy was low ($< 62\%$), this work had a great impact. This spurred two branches: multimodal recognition (visual/acoustic fusion [221]) and applying Personality Recognition to social media (Facebook, X (formerly known as Twitter) [102]). Kosinski M. et al. (2013) highlighted the predictive power of Facebook Likes, simultaneously raising privacy concerns. The 2010s saw rapid growth in text-based Personality Recognition, formalizing two approaches: top-down, exploiting psycholinguistic resources as features and bottom-up, using unsupervised techniques like bag-of-words [16, 246] to extract features from data. Mohammadi and Vinciarelli (2012) advanced the field with audio features, then, shared tasks (2013-2014) [45, 47] provided crucial comparative arenas. Vinciarelli A. et al. (2014) published an influential survey defining the field’s tasks. Subsequent work demonstrated that computer models can outperform humans in personality assessment [293]. Farnadi G. et al. (2016) provided a seminal comparative analysis, setting SotA results for both classification and regression. Later work saw the rise of Deep Learning [247, 285, 286] and systematic meta-analysis showing improved accuracy when including demographics and multimodal features [14]. Research extended to other countries (e.g., China) and languages (e.g., Bahasa [208]), requiring adaptation and optimization techniques like

Fig. 2. Scopus citation network of the works cited in this article with in-degree above 5.

semi-supervised learning and fine-tuning with models like BERT [115], IndoBERT [153], and pre-trained language models with ensemble majority voting [198].

In sum, the past research in Personality Computing tended to focus on the following aspects: the model of personality traits to predict (Big Five, MBTI); the type of data and, in the case of text, the language; the type of features (bottom-up/top-down approach); the type of algorithms and the type of task (classification, regression).

2.4 Personality Questionnaires

Questionnaires are the key instrument to produce gold standard labeled data for Personality Computing. Measuring personality traits is usually achieved by either self-reported or observer-rating assessments. Self-reported assessments traditionally measure personality using a series of items or questions selected from an inventory. The first text-based questionnaire, the Woodworth Psychoneurotic Inventory [212], was developed to screen recruits for shell shock risks. Personality tests have since evolved, and more specialized instruments are utilized for assessment, like the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory [57], the **Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (16PF)** [42], and the **Eysenck Personality Questionnaire - Revised (EPQ-R)** [29]. The most commonly used text-based questionnaires are presented in Table 1. The self-assessment requires that the subject takes the test, while the observer-assessment can be compiled by another person, the observer, and it is also possible to have two or more external observers completing the test in order to have more robust assessments [56]. It is worth noting that the observer assessment method

Table 1. Most Commonly Used Personality Questionnaires

Questionnaire	References	Item count
TIPI	[140]	10
Mini-IPIP	[71]	20
IPIP-IPC-32	[181]	32
Hogan Personality Inventory	[120]	42
BFI-10	[19]	44
NEO-FFI	[61]	60
MBTI	[197]	94
IPIP-FFM	[282]	100
EPQ-R	[29]	100
HEXACO-PI-R	[165]	100
IPIP-NEO-120	[141]	120
BFAS	[95]	40
Woodworth Psychoneurotic Inventory	[212]	116
16PF	[42]	185
California Psychological Inventory	[108]	194
NEO-PI-R	[61, 62]	240

may require monitoring sensitive behavioral data which can expose private conversations or other confidential data, with potential privacy issues. Personality tests can be very short (TIPI with 10 items) to very long (NEO-PI-R with 240 items). On the Internet, however, relying on long text-based questionnaires is often impractical [122]. For this reason, researchers proposed short questionnaires like the **Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI)** [140], and experimental approaches including a visual test [240] and a couple of videogame-based personality assessments [114, 228, 288]. Online environments have proven to be quite rich when it comes to asserting user's characteristics. [48, 82, 213, 226]. Some of the most used social networks in Personality Computing are Facebook, X, Instagram, LinkedIn, Youtube, and the chinese WeChat, Sina Weibo, and RenRen [17]. The characteristics of the social networks environment and the impossibility to control the context when users take the tests online may result in invalid or incomplete assessments. This led to the use of very short personality tests designed for the web, but there are works that show how the use of very short measures of personality may substantially increase both the Type 1 and Type 2 error rates [63].

2.5 Benchmarks and Resources

Personality Computing requires large amounts of data annotated with personality, but collecting data of this kind is difficult and costly. For this reason, there are few very large datasets and many small ones. A summary of benchmarks and resources for Personality Computing used in literature is reported in Table 2.

The first large corpus annotated with personality that became a benchmark is Essays [218], a collection of self descriptions by students who completed the Big Five tests. It contains only elicited text and features are not pre-extracted. Given a great interest in web blogs and social media data, the MyPersonality project [159] started collecting personality data together with digital footprints from Facebook between 2007 and 2015. With 6 millions users collected, this is the largest corpus annotated with personality ever produced, and contains different types of assessments, network structures, Facebook likes, profile pictures, demographic information and other types of digital footprints.

Table 2. Main Benchmarks and Resources for Personality Computing, By Type, language, Available Data Points (Persons), and Dimensions (Features)

Benchmarks	Type	Public	Language	Persons	Features	Reference
Essays	text	no	eng	≈ 2,500	1	[218]
EAR	audio	no	eng	96	1	[179]
Speaker Personality Corpus	audio	no	eng	11	≈ 100	[178]
PersIA	audio	no	eng	22	6,552	[130]
MyPersonality corpus	mixed	yes	mixed	≈ 6,000,000	≈ 50	[158]
Mission Survival Corpus	mixed	no	ita	48	22	[221]
IS2012 speaker trait challenge	audio	no	eng	322	6,125	[245]
WCPR2013	text	yes	eng	250	18	[47]
WCPR2014	mixed	yes	eng	≈ 460	≈ 40	[45]
PAN-AP-2015	text	yes	multi	294	9	[233]
MBTItweets	text	yes	eng	1500	2	[223]
Big5Mbti	text	yes	multi	1,800	1,078	[44]
PANDORA talks	text	yes	eng	≈ 10,000	1	[99]
WASSA	text	yes	eng	≈ 1,000	≈ 20	[21]
Personality Simulation 1	tabular	yes	-	400	≈ 100	[276]
Resources	Type	Public	Language	Entries	Features	
LIWC	text	no	multi	12,000 words	88	[217]
MRC	text	yes	eng	150,837 words	26	[55]
OpenSMILE	audio	yes	-	-	15	[78]
Computational Aesthetics	image	no	-	-	16	[249]

MyPersonality has been used in many works [16, 40, 80, 83, 113, 158, 160, 227] and had a great impact on research in the field. The Mission Survival Corpus [221] is the first multimodal (audio and video tracks) dataset annotated with personality, the first audio corpus is instead the **Speaker Personality Corpus (SPC)** [178], followed by the Speaker Trait Challenge dataset [245]. The Workshop on Computational Personality Recognition 2013 (WCPR2013) [47] and 2014 (WCPR2014) [45] were the first shared tasks that released publicly available corpora for Personality Recognition. WCPR2013 released a corpus with social media text data and network structure of a small and anonymized part of MyPersonality, while WCPR2014 released two datasets: one with mobile data and one with vlogs [30, 31] containing transcriptions and features extracted from video. The PAN Author Profiling shared task in 2015 (PAN-AP-2015) [233] contained personality annotations for 294 X users and their posts. Personality traits were self-assessed with the BFI-10 [19]. PersIA [130] is an audio dataset with simulated tourist call center conversations annotated with the personality of the caller. After the introduction of a very fast search method for automatically extracting textual information annotated with MBTI personality tests from X [223] and from the PersonalityCafé forum [239], a very interesting collected dataset was Big5Mbti [44], the first to contain text data of X users annotated both with Big Five and MBTI labels. Another dataset annotated with both labels is PANDORA talks, a large corpus of text taken from Reddit [99]. The Popularity of MBTI personality types, especially outside of academia, is clear in the fact that the MBTI-type dataset is freely available on Kaggle for competitions. Interestingly, a very recent trend is to generate data using LLMs, which are able to produce synthetic data with specific characteristics of personality, like depressive, obsessive, paranoid or narcissistic, but not specific Big Five personality scores [199]. Since 2022, the WASSA competition includes a shared task on Personality Recognition from text [21], among other tasks like empathy and emotion recognition. Finally, the Personality Simulation 1 dataset, designed for Personality Synthesis, has been recently released in the

Table 3. SotA in Personality Computing

Personality Recognition	Data and target	Article type	F1	Acc	Rho	Reference
IS2012 speaker trait challenge	audio, Big Five	shared task		0.683		[245]
WCPR2013	text, Big Five	shared task	0.720	0.563		[47]
WCPR2014	mixed, Big Five	shared task	0.670	0.620		[45]
PAN-AP-2015	text, Big Five	shared task	*0.711	0.840		[233]
WASSA2022	text, Big Five	shared task			0.230	[21]
WASSA2023	text, Big Five	shared task			0.252	[20]
WASSA2024	text, Big Five	shared task			0.300	[98]
PANDORA talks	text, Big Five+MBTI	open science	0.660		0.292	[99]
Peters and Matz 2024	text, Big Five	open science			0.290	[219]
Personality Synthesis	Data and target	Article type	F1	Acc	Rho	Reference
Klinkert et al. 2024	GPT-4, Big Five	open science		0.740		[157]
Wang et al. 2024	GPT-4, Big Five	open science		0.766		[275]
Personality Perception	Data and target	Article type	F1	Acc	Rho	Reference
Hinds et al. 2024	mixed, Big Five	survey			**0.300	[119]

Metrics Include F1-Measure (F1) and Accuracy (Acc) for Classification Evaluations, and Correlation Coefficients (Rho) for Regression Evaluations. Results show the aggregated performance on all the personality traits reported in the original works. *=replication study. **=Includes approaches that may not be fully comparable.

American Psychological Association (APA) repository [276]. Among the resources used for Personality Computing with top-down methods, one of the most important is LIWC. LIWC was originally developed as a dictionary mapping words to psycholinguistic dimensions, such as the use of first-person, negations, pronouns, and so on. LIWC is now a software [36, 217] that provides APIs in more than one language. **Medical Research Council (MRC)** is a psycholinguistic database [55, 279] that contains a dictionary of 98538 words. MRC features are counts of nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, pronouns, interjections, past participle, and others. There are also resources for top-down feature extraction from multimedia. OpenSMILE [78] is a common software used for the extraction of prosodic and technical features from audio and speech. Computational Aesthetics [249] is an extraction tool that maps images into easily interpretable visual aspects, like color diversity, number of details and rule of thirds. The same tools for the extraction of features from images can be used in the extraction from videos, adding the time feature. The bottom-up approach does not rely on proper resources, but rather on code libraries and algorithms, like n-grams, bag-of-words or features extracted with **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)**. More recent approaches rely on LLMs. LLMs, trained on massive text and code datasets, learn intricate patterns in human language, including personality. Combining top-down and bottom up approaches, LLMs can address Personality Synthesis tasks as well as Personality Recognition even without any example (zero-shot prompting).

2.6 State-of-the-art

In order to report the SotA in Personality Computing in a consistent manner, we narrowed our selection to shared tasks, surveys, and articles³ that target Big Five traits, adhere to open science principles (i.e., provide open data and code), and employ the most widely adopted metrics: F-measure, accuracy, or the correlation coefficient (Rho). Results, reported in Table 3, summarize the SotA in all tasks of Personality Computing. Personality Recognition task is simple: given a set of personality

³Most of the resources and papers were identified through general web searches, as well as searches in Google Scholar and Scopus.

assessments and related digital footprints, this task predicts personality scores or classes from the digital footprints, like text or multimedia. Early shared tasks in Personality Recognition, like the InterSpeech Speaker Trait Challenge 2012, the WCPR2013 and 2014, and the PAN Author Profiling, evaluated personality as classes, measured with F1-score and accuracy averaged over the five traits [99]. Here, the SotA was slightly above 0.7 of F1 measure, with an accuracy ranging between 0.62 and 0.84 depending on the type of input data. The WASSA competition adopted averaged correlation coefficients (ρ), that targets personality traits as scores, and is rapidly becoming the standard to evaluate Personality Recognition. The actual SotA for Personality Recognition from text is an average correlation around 0.3 over a baseline of 0.133, emerged from the WASSA shared tasks [98]. Recent findings report that GPT-3.5 and GPT-4, despite not being specifically trained for Personality Prediction, can infer the Big Five personality traits from users' Facebook status updates with an average correlation of 0.29 with zero-shot prompting. Although there are differences between traits, the averaged result is comparable to that of sophisticated machine learning models explicitly designed for personality inference [219]. A replication study on the PAN-AP-2015 task with the T5 LLM [229] and zero-shot prompting obtained an averaged F1-measure of 0.711 [277], which is in line with most of the machine learning based systems participating to the competition in 2015, suggesting that the SotA is still around a F1 measure of 0.7.

The Personality Synthesis task is more complex: a set of ground truth personality scores are used to create role-play setting prompts that a LLM will execute. The evaluation is done by asking the LLM to complete a self-assessment assuming each role-played character and measuring the consistency of the assessment results. Although there are different metrics in literature for this task, such as accuracy and Cronbach's alpha averaged over the five traits, there are works comparable by means of averaged accuracy. The SotA in this task is an averaged accuracy around 0.75. Finally, the Personality Perception task is the most complex one, involving the comparison between human and machine judgments of personality derived from digital footprints. In this task, personality is operationally defined as Inter-Rater Agreement, specifically the consistency (i.e., effect sizes) among ratings from different human judges (observers) for the same target individual. Results are typically measured using the **Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC)**, or occasionally, the Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance (Kendall's W) for non-parametric assessment [154]. Sometimes, the results are also compared against the scores provided by self-assessments, to understand the difference between self-perception and others' perception. Recent work [119] made an extensive meta analysis of more than 30 studies on Personality Perception. Their research investigates the convergent validity of self-reported personality with both human perception and Personality Computing systems. Meta-analyses of human perception studies found moderate convergent validity across the Big Five traits ($\rho = 0.38$). A meta-analysis of computer prediction studies demonstrated a convergent validity of $\rho = 0.30$, and this is the reference SotA in computational Personality Perception, which is close to the human convergent validity. However, effect sizes of this study must be interpreted with caution as the human and computer perception experimental settings used different methods, data sets, and approaches that may not be fully comparable. Despite this, the meta-analysis identified that data sources (e.g., social media, videos, smartphone data) have a significant impact on the variance explained. In other words, the communication channels affect the way personality is perceived.

3 Personality Computing Systems

Personality Computing systems have different components, including pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification/generation. Typically, systems that employ machine learning should be designed and trained in all the distinct parts, systems based on Deep Learning automate the pre-processing and feature extraction part, while LLM-based systems have a complete automation,

but are less transparent. In this section, we present an overview of the main Personality Computing systems, divided into text-based, image-based, audio-based, video-based, hybrid systems (based on other sources of data such as social media metadata, mobile phone data, etc.) and LLM-based systems. Note that our overview is in line with the PRISMA 2020 guidance [211]. An important aspect of PRISMA 2020 is the methodology used to obtain a comprehensive and relevant set of works. Relevant works were identified by combining multiple keywords (e.g., “text”, “image”) with various aliases for personality systems (e.g., “personality classification”, “personality categorization”, “personality computing” or simply “personality”) in searches conducted on the general web and scientific databases. Since this strategy alone was insufficient, we also examined the reference lists of the retrieved articles and expanded the corpus iteratively, effectively forming a kind of transitive closure until no additional relevant resources could be identified. The completeness of this approach was verified by analyzing Scopus citation networks using the Gephi visualization tool. This first phase was intentionally inclusive, meaning that no works were initially discarded. In the second, “pruning” phase, each article was subjected to a thorough analysis, with particular attention given to preprints. Articles exhibiting inconsistencies or methodological flaws, for example, small sample sizes, inadequate training/validation/testing setups, or failure to compare with relevant methods from the literature, were excluded from the set of considered works. For instance, in Souri et al. [252], the authors introduce a newly created Facebook dataset of 100 respondents and apply several methods. Inevitably, one of these methods outperforms the others, and the authors present it as their proposed approach, coincidentally a Boosting Decision Tree implemented through the RapidMiner toolbox. However, this type of research provides little added value, particularly as no data or code are made available for replication or further improvement. Consequently, we excluded this article from consideration. Valid articles were reviewed by a single reviewer, whereas for articles identified as potential candidates for exclusion, at least one additional reviewer was involved in the decision process. A similar approach was applied in the data collection process: when no inconsistencies were detected, a single reviewer was sufficient, while additional reviewers were consulted in cases where discrepancies were identified. Following the PRISMA 2020 flow chart structure, we identified 163 records in the identification phase. After removing duplicates, 152 records remained. During the screening phase, 26 articles were excluded for the previously stated reasons. In total, the review included 45 papers on text-based systems, 15 on image-based systems, 7 on audio-based systems, 25 on video-based systems, 20 on hybrid systems, 7 on LLM-based Personality Computing systems, and an additional 10 articles on LLM ethics in Personality Computing systems. An extensive elaboration of the PRISMA procedure is provided as supplementary material available online at https://poincare.matf.bg.ac.rs/~aleksandar.kartelj/PRISMA_2020.pdf.

3.1 Text-based Systems

There are many Personality Computing systems based on text, categorized and reported in Table 4. These systems are based mainly on English, but they employ relatively large datasets in terms of subjects. We grouped similar algorithms (e.g., AdaBoost [92], XGBoost [50], and Gradient Boosting into the “Boosting” category) and applied similar groupings to data types and features. Our analysis revealed that, among the systems for Personality Recognition from text, **Support Vector Machines (SVMs)** [60] were the most frequently used algorithms (20 articles) before the introduction of Neural Networks (12 articles). Surprisingly, Naive Bayes is well represented (10 articles). Notably, the use of Neural Networks has significantly increased in recent years. Regarding data sources, social network data is the most frequent source, appearing in 27 articles. Essays were also a frequently used benchmark, in 15 studies. While weblogs were prominent in earlier years, their usage has declined since 2011. Psycho-linguistic features were the most common homogeneous feature category (16 articles), although a slightly higher number of articles (20) utilized a broader range of general

Table 4. Text-based Systems

		Algorithms										Data type					Features																		
Published	Reference	Bayesian multinomial regression	Boosting	Conditional random fields	Decision tree	Gaussian process	Lazy learners	Logistic regression	Linear Discriminant Analysis	Memory-based learning	Naive Bayes	Nearest neighbors	Neural networks	Random forest	Receptiviti API	Ridge regression	Rule-based learners	Sequential minimal optimization	Support vector machine	Stochastic Gradient descent	Blogs and weblogs	Electronically Activated Recorder	Emails	Essays	MyPersonality	Social networks	Metadata and activity	Non-lexical synthetic	N-grams	Other lexical (word-based)	Part-Of-Speech	Psycho-linguistic (LIWC, MRC,...)	Semantic		
2006	[207]									✓								✓									✓								
2006	[178]				✓									✓							✓	✓								✓		✓			
2007	[76]		✓		✓	✓							✓			✓					✓	✓							✓	✓		✓			
2008	[175]									✓														✓							✓				
2009	[11]	✓																			✓		✓						✓	✓					
2011	[190]									✓											✓								✓						
2011	[226]					✓																			✓		✓								
2011	[103]						✓																	✓								✓			
2011	[200]							✓										✓			✓											✓			
2011	[129]																			✓												✓			
2012	[259]				✓					✓			✓													✓		✓					✓		
2012	[155]																							✓								✓	✓		
2013	[49]							✓		✓			✓												✓				✓						
2013	[225]																								✓								✓		
2013	[83]									✓	✓											✓	✓	✓			✓		✓			✓	✓		
2013	[128]		✓					✓		✓							✓						✓	✓	✓				✓						
2013	[192]																							✓									✓		
2013	[265]							✓																✓										✓	
2014	[164]					✓										✓									✓		✓		✓						
2014	[281]																							✓				✓	✓						
2015	[213]															✓								✓											
2016	[101]																								✓									✓	
2016	[263]																								✓									✓	
2017	[294]																									✓		✓							
2018	[27]									✓	✓															✓		✓						✓	
2018	[286]											✓															✓							✓	
2019	[74]		✓	✓							✓	✓	✓												✓	✓	✓							✓	
2019	[289]																									✓			✓						
2019	[163]		✓						✓	✓															✓	✓	✓								
2019	[290]				✓																				✓	✓	✓		✓						
2020	[236]																									✓									
2020	[187]								✓				✓												✓	✓	✓							✓	
2020	[152]																								✓				✓						
2020	[134]													✓												✓			✓	✓	✓				
2020	[188]																									✓									
2021	[273]		✓						✓	✓																			✓						
2021	[12]		✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓														✓	✓	✓						✓	
2021	[287]												✓												✓	✓								✓	
2021	[72]												✓											✓	✓									✓	
2021	[54]												✓												✓									✓	
2022	[230]																								✓										✓
2022	[231]																								✓									✓	
2022	[232]																								✓									✓	
2023	[162]																									✓									✓
2023	[150]			✓				✓		✓	✓	✓													✓				✓						✓
Total articles: 45		1	5	1	8	2	1	8	1	1	10	4	12	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	1	6	2	1	15	12	15	7	4	4	20	5	16	3

Table 5. Big Five Cues in Textual Data

Trait	Level	Behavior	Reference
O	High	Avoidance of past tense, use of words related to insight.	[186]
		Low usage of parentheses. Update their statuses by using dictionary words, social interaction words, affective processes, cues associated with hearing, 2nd person singular and 3rd person plural pronouns.	[103] [83]
	Low	Religious institutions, activity words.	[129]
C	High	Males produce more filler words.	[186]
		Use of 2nd person pronouns in males.	[186]
		Not using of words about death, and with negative emotion.	[103]
		Use of 'you'.	[103]
		Use of language that denotes planning, outcome, evaluation.	[129]
	Low	Often present cues associated with the five senses and interaction words, affective processes, cues associated with hearing, 2nd person singular and 3rd person plural pronouns.	[83]
	Low	Use of second-person pronouns in females.	[186]
E	High	Less formal language in e-mails.	[206]
		Low usage of parentheses.	[103]
		Use of fewer words per sentence, use more leisure, number, money, and percept words.	[200]
		Strong curse words, talk location, use of social words, words suggesting positive emotional valience, more self-reference words, more often use of 1st person singular.	[129]
		Many friends who in turn are not friends with each other; preference for using dictionary words, 2nd and 3rd person singular pronouns, past tense words, social interaction words, cues associated with the five senses, health related words, and not swear words.	[83]
		Language reflecting positive emotion, enthusiasm, and sociability.	[213]
	Low	Formal greetings in e-mails and first person singular Pronouns	[206]
More swear, health words and negations.		[200]	
Higher usage of possessive, use of more time-related language. Inward focused language, greater interest in things and tentativeness.		[129] [213]	
A	High	Use of 'you'.	[103]
	Low	Use of positive words. Swearing.	[129] [186]
N	High	Referring to oneself, use of pronouns as subjects in a clause, use of reflexive pronouns. Anger words in status updates; less likely to use social interaction words, positive emotions and prepositions.	[11] [83]
	Low	Less concreteness in writing, less precise specifications of object and events, more concern with how things are or should be (by using 'by', 'with', 'ought', 'should'). Use of thoughtful words (reflect on, chose to).	[11] [129]

word-based features. In terms of research activity, a relatively consistent trend is observed, with a slight surge between 2011 and 2013 and a renewed increase after 2019.

It is well known that words convey attitudes that can be seen as cues for Personality Perception. Table 5 summarizes cues that link textual content to the Big Five personality traits. For instance, research suggests that extraverts, while using fewer curse words, tend to use them more forcefully [129, 200]. Conscientious individuals, along with those high in Openness and Agreeableness, are more likely to use second-person pronouns [103], moreover, women low in Conscientiousness also exhibit this tendency [186]. Interestingly, studies have linked low Openness to the use of religious terminology [129] and Extraversion to less formality in their e-mails [206]. Among the dark-triad traits there are correlations between Narcissism and the use of hashtags and sex-related words, Machiavellianism and swear words/anger, and Psychopathy and swear words/anger/death [259]. The extraction of an open vocabulary analysis of social media language, identified specific words and distinct linguistic patterns associated to different personality traits [213], for example extraverts use words like “love”, “party”, “tonight”, while introverts use more words like “computer” and “don’t”; neurotics use “really”, “hate”, “anymore”, conscientious individuals use “great”, “family” and “wonderful”; people scoring low in Agreeableness use “fuck”, “shit”, and “ass”, while those with predicted high Openness to experience use “into”, “through”, and “world”.

Table 6. Image-based Systems

		Algorithms										Features								
Published	Reference	Decision tree	Gaussian process	Linear regression and extensions	Logistic regression	Multiple instance learning	Naïve Bayes	Nearest neighbors	Neural networks	Random forest	Rule-based	Support vector machine	Data source	Color-based (brightness, hue, saturation...)	Composition	CNN implied features	Other (SIFT, SURF, HOG, ...)	People (count, pose, gender, ...)	Texture (LBP, GLCM, GIST, Tamura, ...)	Visual words (or their pyramids)
2014	[43]	✓		✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	Facebook				✓			✓
2014	[4]											✓	FERET				✓			
2015	[85]								✓				Instagram	✓				✓		
2015	[111]											✓	Sina Weibo	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
2016	[86]	✓											Instagram	✓			✓			
2016	[249]					✓		✓					PsychoFlick	✓	✓		✓	✓		
2016	[112]			✓								✓	Flickr	✓	✓		✓	✓		
2016	[283]		✓										Flickr	✓	✓		✓	✓		
2017	[248]								✓			✓	Flickr			✓				
2017	[110]			✓								✓	X	✓	✓					
2017	[247]			✓	✓								Facebook	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2018	[87]	✓							✓	✓			Instagram	✓	✓					
2018	[88]								✓				Instagram			✓	✓			
2020	[145]								✓				Volunteers			✓				
2021	[284]								✓				Students			✓				
Total articles: 15		3	1	3	2	1	1	2	7	2	1	6		9	4	7	5	6	5	3

3.2 Image-based Systems

Image-based Personality Recognition systems make use of different cues from a rich visual signal. Features extracted from pictures typically account for colors (brightness, saturation, hue), composition (pleasure-arousal-dominance, **Scale-Invariant Feature Transform - SIFT** [174]), and content.

In general, these systems use relatively large datasets and are not constrained to any language, but heavily rely on data from social media. Table 6 summarizes 15 studies (2014-2021) on personality inference from images of different nature, from profile pictures to images posted on different social media. Neural Networks and SVMs are the most common algorithms, with CNNs usage increasing for the automatic extraction of features. Data sources vary, and features include automatically detected attributes, image filters, computer vision features (SIFT, Speeded Up Robust Features-SURF [25], Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF-ORB [238]), and color characteristics (e.g., saturation, hue). Openness is associated with complex, artistic images and drawings, often including drawings and abstract art. Their pictures may also exhibit unconventional compositions and fewer details, fewer faces, and lower engagement with others' photos [110, 248]. Conscientiousness is linked to conventional, detailed images, landscapes, buildings, and more faces, with selfies revealing fewer private locations [249]. Findings on the association between Conscientiousness and black-and-white images are inconsistent [112]. Extraversion is strongly correlated with the number of people/faces in images [247]. Introverts also post drawings and art, but less frequently than open individuals

Table 7. Audio-based Systems

Published Reference	Algorithms					Data source	Features			
	Linear regression	Random forest	Support vector machine	AdaBoost	Ordinal regression		LIWC	MRC	prosodic	openSMILE features
2007 [179]		✓	✓			EAR and essays	✓	✓	✓	
2010 [224]			✓			Actor audio logs			✓	
2010 [195]			✓			News bulletins from Radio Suisse Romande			✓	
2012 [194]	✓					News bulletins from Radio Suisse Romande			✓	
2012 [193]				✓		News bulletins from Radio Suisse Romande			✓	
2013 [5]		✓	✓	✓		Speaker Personality Corpus and Personable and Intelligent virtual Agents corpus			✓	
2014 [6]		✓	✓	✓		Speaker Personality Corpus and Personable and Intelligent virtual Agents corpus			✓	
Total articles: 7	1	2	5	3	1		1	1	5	2

[110]. Low Agreeableness is characterized by fewer colors, high grayscale usage, and fewer people or only self-portraits [43]. Agreeable individuals exhibit more diverse color usage and may share similar visual characteristics with extroverts. High Neuroticism is often associated with grayscale and darker images, and their images may exhibit lower levels of pleasure and higher levels of arousal, although one study found the opposite [247]. Low Neuroticism is linked to images featuring other people, nature, and brighter colors [86].

3.3 Audio, Video, and Hybrid systems

Systems that compute personality from audio signals face language dependency, though English is less dominant in this field compared to text-based systems. A common limitation across audio systems is their reliance on relatively small number of subjects.

Many acoustic cues relate to personality, such as pitch and intensity [67], with Extraverted people often speaking louder, faster, and with fewer hesitations [235]. Dedicated audio-only Personality Computing systems are less common today due to the prevalence of multimodal, hybrid, and LLM-based approaches (Table 7). Early work by Mairesse et al. (2007) [179] combined LIWC and prosodic features from audio diaries and essays, finding that prosodic features were crucial for Extraversion (which was best classified by AdaboostM1) and that speech cues were significant for Neuroticism perception, while Conscientiousness was linked to voice intensity variation. Subsequently, Mohammadi and Vinciarelli (2010, 2012) [194, 195] confirmed the critical relevance of prosodic features (pitch, energy, speaking rate) for predicting observer-attributed traits, achieving high accuracy with SVMs, especially for Extraversion and Conscientiousness. Furthermore, Alam et al. (2014) [6] demonstrated that fusing lexical and prosodic characteristics consistently improves speaker personality recognition across corpora.

Video is a pervasive multimedia containing also audio, thus providing rich features with spontaneous nonverbal behavior for Personality Computing, Big Five cues are summarized in Table 9.

Audiovisual-based systems offer advantages as they are less susceptible to language dependencies, and they leverage rich sources of information often available in relatively large datasets. As reported in table 8, the features employed are diverse, encompassing verbal/non-verbal behavior (e.g., whether a character speaks), recognized emotions (anger, happiness, etc.), dialog time, number of people present, gesture/object detection, and technical features (pitch, prosody, colors) [253]. Biel et al. (2013) [33] found unique correlations for Conscientiousness with linguistic features like auxiliary verbs and articles. Key findings emphasize the role of specific cues: Lepri et al. (2012) [168] showed that the attention received while silent was sufficient to classify Extraversion, a finding supported

Table 8. Video-based Systems

Published Reference	Algorithms					Data source							Features											
	Linear regression	Ridge regression	Random forest	Support vector machine	Naive Bayes	Hidden Markov Models	Neural networks	Mission Survival Corpus 1	Mission Survival Corpus 2	Cocktel party corpus	Short self-introductions	Vlogs	EAR corpus	Movie clips	Social media videos	ChalLearn dataset	Acoustic	Visual	Proxemic	Automatically detected	LIWC, MRC, etc	N-grams	Statistics based	Time and frequency domain
2008 [221]			✓					✓								✓								
2009 [166]			✓					✓									✓	✓						
2010 [296]			✓						✓										✓					
2010 [146]				✓				✓									✓	✓						
2010 [167]			✓					✓									✓	✓						
2011 [24]			✓	✓						✓							✓	✓						
2011 [255]			✓	✓	✓			✓									✓	✓						
2011 [30]	✓											✓	✓							✓				
2012 [168]			✓					✓									✓	✓						
2012 [31]			✓									✓					✓	✓						
2012 [22]			✓							✓							✓							
2012 [32]			✓									✓							✓					
2012 [253]			✓											✓			✓	✓						
2013 [33]			✓	✓								✓								✓	✓			
2013 [256]			✓	✓	✓				✓										✓					
2013 [10]		✓	✓									✓						✓						✓
2014 [242]	✓													✓			✓	✓		✓				
2014 [6]			✓											✓			✓	✓		✓				
2016 [81]			✓	✓										✓			✓	✓		✓				
2017 [270]							✓										✓	✓						
2018 [148]							✓										✓	✓						
2019 [13]							✓									✓	✓	✓						
2020 [292]			✓							✓														✓
2021 [251]							✓									✓			✓					
2022 [258]							✓								✓				✓					
Total articles: 25	2	1	3	17	4	1	5	4	2	2	3	5	1	1	4	4	15	15	2	3	4	1	1	1

by Personality Psychology [269]. Biel et al. (2012) [31] identified Extraversion and Emotional Stability as the traits associated with the largest and fewest informative cues, respectively, noting that Extraversion impressions relate to both audio and visual data, while Conscientiousness and Agreeableness relate more to visual data. They also showed that facial expression cues are more valuable than previously used visual cues and that verbal content is particularly useful for predicting Agreeableness, Emotional Stability, and Conscientiousness [33]. Furthermore, Subramanian et al. (2013) [256] found that combining audiovisual features and facial expressions significantly boosts performance, particularly for Extraversion, and that attentional features yield the best classification performance for Extraversion, while minimum distance features work well for Neuroticism.

In the context of Personality Computing, “hybrid systems” refer to the integration of multiple computational approaches and multiple data sources to achieve a more robust and accurate understanding of personality.

Table 9. Big Five Cues in Video Data

Trait	Level	Behavior	Reference
O	High	Leaning toward the camera more	[24]
		Showing upper body alongside face	[31]
		More movement	[31]
		Use of words related to leisure activities and words concerning senses	[33]
		Expressing negative emotions less frequently	[33]
	Receiving higher level of attention from the audience	[31]	
Low	Gesticulate more	[24]	
	Looking at the camera for longer	[31]	
C	High	Higher with age	[24]
		Smiling more	[24]
		Lower pitch and lower minimal vocal energy and produce shorter voiced segments	[24]
		Longer speaking time	[30]
		Receiving higher level of attention from the audience	[31]
		looking at the camera longer and more persistently	[31]
	Large amounts of looking while speaking time	[31]	
	Increased use of words describing occupation and achievement, decreased use of negative emotion words, swearing words, and sexual words	[33]	
	Use of auxiliary verbs, present tense, positive association with articles, prepositions, and inclusive words, positive correlation to the length of words	[33]	
	Low	Use smaller part of presentations for speaking	[24]
More frequent head movements		[24]	
More movement		[31]	
Use of single person pronoun singular I		[33]	
E	High	Extraverts/introverts do not differ simply because of the amount of social gaze they receive, but because of the general gaze behavior, they induce in the rest of the group.	[167]
		Women are higher in extraversion	[24]
		Give and receive more attention while speaking	[168]
		Receiving higher level of attention from the audience	[31]
		Longer speaking time and longer speaking segments, high fluency	[31]
		Speaking louder with higher pitch	[31]
		Showing upper body alongside face	[31]
		More movement	[31]
	Large amounts of looking while speaking time	[31]	
	Use of 2nd person singular pronouns and sexual words	[33]	
Low	More speech turns	[30], [31]	
	Give and receive more attention while silent	[168]	
	Looking at the camera for longer	[31]	
	Large amounts of looking while not speaking time	[31]	
Use more cognitive-related words, including discrepancy, tentative and exclusive words	[33]		
A	High	Straight posture	[24]
		Lower pitch	[24]
		Producing longer presentations	[24]
		Vloggers extremely high in conscientiousness receive more attention	[31]
		Showing upper body alongside face	[31]
	Use of both positive and negative emotion words, self-references, and friendship	[33]	
Low	Vloggers extremely low in conscientiousness receive more attention	[31]	
	Are rated lower by others	[31]	
	Use of 'they'	[33]	
	Use of anger, negative emotion words, words related to sexuality, swear words, body states, and religion	[33]	
N	High	Higher amount of gesticulation, and higher vocal intensity	[24]
	Low	Men are more emotionally stable	[24]
		Greater number of short-leaning forward events	[24]
		Large amounts of looking while speaking time	[31]
Do not use negative emotional words, negative words, swear, and sexual words	[33]		

Table 10. Hybrid Systems

Published	Reference	Algorithms										Data source						Features									
		Linear regression	Logistic regression	ZeroR regression	Decision tree	Random forest	Support vector machine	Naive Bayes	M5 rules	ELM, ULFI and BERT	Neural networks	Gaussian processes	Social network metadata	Phone call records	Smartphone usage data	Sociometric badge data	Emails	Essays	EEG data	Phone usage based	Body movements based	N-grams, bag-of-words	LIWC, LDA, Word2Vec topic features	EEG signal power spectra based	Automatically detected	Other based on metadata	
2011	[102]	✓						✓			✓														✓		
2011	[66]						✓						✓												✓		
2011	[52]			✓		✓								✓											✓		
2012	[227]	✓											✓												✓		
2012	[18]				✓		✓	✓					✓												✓		
2012	[16]	✓			✓		✓						✓												✓		
2012	[209]				✓								✓												✓		
2012	[254]					✓								✓											✓		
2013	[160]	✓	✓										✓												✓		
2013	[147]						✓										✓	✓			✓						
2013	[7]		✓				✓	✓					✓									✓					
2013	[53]						✓							✓						✓							
2013	[271]						✓						✓					✓				✓					
2014	[201]	✓											✓												✓		
2014	[158]	✓											✓												✓		
2014	[1]			✓							✓		✓	✓					✓						✓		
2018	[72]								✓				✓				✓				✓	✓					
2018	[274]				✓									✓						✓							
2020	[169]									✓								✓						✓			
2023	[28]										✓							✓					✓	✓			
Total articles: 20		6	2	1	5	1	8	2	1	1	1	3	12	2	4	1	1	2	2	3	1	3	1	2	3	10	

Hybrid Personality Computing systems usually combine text with various metadata (e.g., social media ego networks, smartphone usage, EEG data) to mitigate language/platform dependency and data limitations.

A review of these systems (see Table 10) shows the primary models used are SVMs (8), Linear Regression (6), and Decision Trees (5), with the most common data sources being social media metadata (12) and smartphone usage/call data (6). The diverse nature of the data leads to significant variation in feature extraction. Influential examples include Golbeck et al. (2011), who combined Facebook friend networks and LIWC text features to predict traits using Linear Regression [102], and Chittaranjan et al. (2011), who linked smartphone usage patterns (app use, calls, SMS) to specific traits (e.g., Conscientiousness with office apps; Introversion with less internet use) [52]. Other studies showed that social media metadata like friendship count and activity level are highly informative, particularly for Extraversion [18, 158].

Adali et al. (2014) found varying predictive accuracy across traits using mixed communication data, with Openness and Agreeableness being the most predictable [1]. More recently, Elmadjian et al. (2022) improved personality classification by fusing features from multiple advanced pre-trained language models (ELMo, ULFI, BERT) across benchmark datasets, demonstrating enhanced average accuracy, with BERT generally outperforming others [72].

<p>PROMPT</p> <p>Play the role of a person with the following Big Five personality scores: Extraversion: 35, Neuroticism: 18, Agreeableness 29, Conscientiousness 21, Openness to experience: 24. Rate the following sentence with a score from 1 (very accurate) to 5 (not accurate): ``I am the life of the party''.</p> <p>RESPONSE</p> <p>Given my high Extraversion score of 35, which indicates a strong tendency to seek out social interactions and enjoy being the focus of attention, I rated myself as ``Very Accurate'' for statement 1, ``Am the life of the party.'' This suggests that I am outgoing, lively, and quite comfortable in social settings, much like someone who could be described as the ``life of the party.''</p>
--

Fig. 3. Example of psychometric prompting for role-playing experiments on personality reasoning with GPT-4.

Findings of some of the most important articles with hybrid systems is reported in Table 11. Key findings often correlate personality to social network size, online activity (e.g., status updates, messaging), and mobile device usage (e.g., app engagement, internet browsing, device modes).

3.4 LLM-based Systems

LLMs like GPT-4, Gemini, and LLaMa have revolutionized natural language processing and AI, offering unprecedented potential for psychological research as well as for Personality Computing. Recent research explored the foundational principles of LLMs, explaining how they generate human-like text without possessing human-like consciousness. For example the human reasoning behind a response to the questionnaire item “I am the life of the party” would include memory of past experiences, while GPT-4 follows a different type of reasoning, as reported in Figure 3.

In particular, LLMs generate responses that align with the expected personality profile. They exhibit dynamic and context-dependent outputs that resemble personality states but differ from human experience. GPT-4 demonstrates a remarkable ability to emulate human personality in a role-playing scenario by directly mapping questionnaire items to Big Five traits. While the underlying reasoning process may differ from that of humans, GPT-4’s emulated personality scores exhibit high levels of validity, both in terms of consistency with other measures of the same trait (convergent validity) and in terms of distinctiveness from other personality traits (discriminant validity) [276]. However, this performance appears to diminish as the complexity of the role-playing scenario increases. Furthermore, incorporating demographic information alongside personality traits, while consistent, can influence the overall level and accuracy of emulated personality scores for certain traits [276].

Personality Computing systems based on LLMs, reported in Table 12, are able to take as input any kind of source, including multimedia, and generate as output text, audio, code, pictures, and even video. Most articles used GPT-3 and GPT-4. We analyzed 7 articles and found that the application of Personality Computing on textual data for Personality Recognition continues also with LLMs, followed by the Personality Synthesis task. While zero-shot and few-shot prompting are commonly employed for Personality Recognition, role-play prompting is the most common technique for Personality Synthesis. We also note a rising trend in the prediction of MBTI traits in place of Big Five. Previous work demonstrated that MBTI labels are easier to classify than Big Five scores [44]. Gan et al. [96] addressed the issue of Personality Perception from pictures. The authors compiled a new personality dataset of 41,800 facial images labeled with perceived MBTI personality types and employed zero-shot prompting for facial image Personality Perception tasks. They claim to achieve statistically significant results ($p < 0.01$) in predicting all the perceived MBTI traits, but effect sizes

Table 11. Big Five Cues in Hybrid Systems

Trait	Level	Behavior	Reference
O	High	Longer favorite books lists	[102]
		Lower likelihood of missing calls and of sending SMS	[52]
		Higher usage of social media	[18]
		Positively correlated with the number of users' likes, group association, and status updates	[16]
		Following more people	[201]
	Low	Tendency to like more items on Facebook. Mentioning others more (via hashtags); writing longer messages	[158]
		Denser friend networks	[102]
		Higher usage of the office app	[52]
		Higher usage of the SMS app	[52]
		Higher number of SMS sent or received	[53]
C	High	Higher likelihood of making phone calls in men	[53]
		Use of words surrounding social processes and words describing people	[102]
		Women significantly higher than man in this trait	[102]
		Higher usage of the office, e-mail and SMS apps	[52]
		More uploaded photos	[16]
	Low	Positive correlation to the use of Normal mode on the phone and negative to the use of all other profiles	[53]
		Higher frequency in use of swear words and words describing perceptual processes	[102]
		Higher likelihood of using Video/Audio/Music apps and the Youtube app	[52], [53]
		Higher number of likes and group memberships	[16]
		Higher likelihood of making phone calls in women	[53]
E	High	Joining more Facebook groups and liking more things	[158]
		Having more friends but sparser friend networks	[102]
		Higher likelihood of receiving phone calls and taking longer calls	[52]
		Having more friends, using emotion in blogs, talking more with others and republishing others' statuses more	[18]
		Positively correlated with status republishing proportion	[18]
	Low	Higher likelihood of reaching out and interacting with other people on Facebook, of liking content posted by their friends. More interactions with people in Facebook groups. Positive correlation to the number of friends	[16]
		Higher likelihood of reaching out and interacting with others on Facebook (especially strangers), sharing more from personal life. Higher number of Facebook friends	[158]
		Writing longer messages, having more outgoing than incoming messages	[1]
		Lower likelihood of using the internet	[52]
		Lower usage of Bluetooth	[52]
A	High	Positively correlated with the use of the Internet, Games, and Camera	[53]
		Higher likelihood of using the Internet app, but only for women	[53]
		Use of affective process words and positive words	[102]
		Women significantly higher than man in this trait	[102]
		Higher likelihood of receiving phone calls	[52]
	Low	More activity in online chatting	[18]
		Higher number of tags	[16]
		Higher likelihood of appearing with friends in photos	[16]
		Somewhat negatively correlated with the number of likes	[16]
		Positive correlation to the use of Normal mode on the phone and negative to the use of all other profiles	[53]
N	High	Sending longer text messages	[53]
		Higher likelihood of making phone calls in men	[53]
		Performing warmly and considerably. Having relatively more mutual followers, and more positive sentiment of self descriptions	[201]
		Mentioning others more (via hashtags)	[1]
		Higher usage of the SMS app	[52]
	Low	Lower usage of Bluetooth	[52]
		Higher usage of Office, Internet, Audio/Video, Music, Mail, Calendar, and SMS apps	[53]
		Use of words expressing anxiety	[102]
		Women significantly higher than man in this trait	[102]
		Higher usage of the e-mail app	[52]
High	Positively correlated with number of angry blogs	[18]	
	More Facebook likes and slightly greater number of groups	[16]	
	Increasing with the number of friends until reaching 200 friends	[16]	
	Higher likelihood of making phone calls in women	[53]	
	Having a preference for posting statuses between 0am and 6am and publishing more statuses	[201]	
Low	More Facebook likes	[158]	
	Higher usage of the Office and Calendar app	[52], [53]	
	Positive correlation to the number of friends	[16]	
	Increasing with the number of friends after 200 friends	[16]	
	Higher likelihood of using the Silent profile, and lower likelihood of using the Ascending and Ring Once profiles	[53]	
		Longer SMS word length in both inbox and sent items	[53]

Table 12. LLM-based Systems

		Prompt Design					Inputs				
Published	Reference	Role-play prompting	Zero-shot Prompting	Few-shot prompting	Meta-prompting	Knowledge distillation prompting	Benchmark (and Task)				
							text	picture	audio	metadata	
2022	[96]		✓	✓			(perception)	✓			
2023	[277]		✓	✓			Essays, MyPersonality, PAN-AP-2015 (recognition)	✓			
2023	[97]		✓				MyPersonality (recognition)	✓		✓	
2024	[219]		✓				MyPersonality (recognition)	✓		✓	
2024	[157]	✓					Open-Source Psychometrics Project (synthesis)			✓	
2024	[121]			✓	✓		Mbti-type (recognition)	✓			
2025	[276]	✓		✓			Simulation 1 (synthesis)	✓			
Total articles: 7		2	2	3	3	2		5	1	0	3

are small (below 0.2 Cohen’s h). Hu et al. [121] introduce a novel Personality Recognition technique that leverages LLM-enabled text augmentation. This model distills valuable knowledge from the LLM into a smaller model, effectively mitigating the challenges of limited data and enhancing the accuracy of MBTI personality classification. In general, good results in Personality Recognition are obtained even with zero-shot prompting, while few-shot prompting and knowledge distillation can help improve the performance. However, the real novelties introduced by LLMs are in the tasks of Personality Synthesis and Personality Perception, where role-playing prompting opens new experimental settings.

3.5 LLMs, Personality, and Ethical Issues

We surveyed peer-reviewed research about LLMs, personality, and ethics, finding that three main themes emerged recently:

- (1) LLMs exhibit personality-like behavioural patterns (Machine Personality) [137];
- (2) these patterns can be shaped or induced in ways that alter LLM behaviour (Personality Hacking) [117];
- (3) altered behaviors of LLMs can be exploited to manipulate individuals through artificial intimacy and social engineering. This highlights an urgent need to protect the human factor within cybersecurity (Personality Safety) [138].

Details are reported in Table 13. A wide range of studies show that LLM-generated content has consistent trait profiles, such as high Agreeableness, high Openness, and low Neuroticism, across tests, prompts, and tasks [26, 137, 138]. These behaviours function as personality-like dispositions, even though they are not psychological states. Whether through psychometric prompting, structured personality descriptions, fine-tuning on personality-grounded dialogue, or architectural adapters, induced personality traits systematically shift LLM reasoning, planning, interaction style, and decision-making [117, 127, 170]. In short, personality is a practical lever for controlling LLM behavior. By adjusting a model’s traits in prompts, malicious users can fine-tune its ethics, its resistance to jailbreaks, and its overall safety and fairness [117]. In general, some traits consistently correlate with safer outputs (e.g., Conscientiousness), while others introduce volatility.

Table 13. LLM, Personality and Ethics Survey

Published References		LLMs							Main Theme
		GPT 3.5	GPT 4	ERNIE 4	Llama 3	Llama 2	Claude 3	Gemini 1.5	
2024	[137]	✓	✓						Machine Personality
2024	[219, 260]	✓	✓						Personality Safety
2025	[26, 127, 138, 257]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Machine Personality
2025	[117, 170]	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Personality Hacking
2025	[143]	✓							Personality Safety
Total articles: 10									

Models such as GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 predict Big Five traits from social media posts with accuracy rivaling supervised systems [219]. This allows virtually anyone to engage in unconsented psychological profiling, raising concerns about privacy, autonomy, and psychological targeting. LLMs generating personalised, value-laden, or emotionally resonant content can trigger artificial intimacy [143], influencing users in ways resembling targeted persuasion [260]. Major concerns include users trusting AI too much, biased personality data, deceptive AI personas, and inaccurate ways of measuring LLM behavior. [118, 143, 170]. The literature agrees that since LLM personality is modifiable and carries ethical risks, it should be treated as a core safety concern requiring dedicated evaluation and oversight [127, 138, 170, 257].

4 Discussion and Conclusion

In this article, we have reviewed questionnaires, benchmarks and resources, and reported the SotA of Personality Computing systems for three different tasks: Personality Recognition, Personality Synthesis and Personality Perception. We also developed a categorization of systems for Personality Computing, including the recent LLM-based systems, and ethical issues related to them.

In general, Personality Computing exploited tools and models from Personality Psychology to explore manifestations of personality on a large scale, often supporting previous findings. An overview of the applications, current challenges, and potential future directions emerge from the analysis.

4.1 Applications and Impact

Personality Computing systems has proven to be useful in many real-world applications. These include marketing [191], entertainment [3], education [241], mental health [58], forensics [73], recommendation systems [237], human-computer interaction [177], and talent acquisition [89]. In marketing, Personality Recognition from text and images helps tailoring advertisements and marketing campaigns to individual personality traits for increased effectiveness [46, 204]. In entertainment, Personality Computing is employed for creating personalized experiences, such as music playlists [189] and game difficulty levels [220]. Other applications include the design of personalized user interfaces [149, 151] such as custom website skins [39]. In addition, personality models are also employed in dating websites to match couples [70, 297]. Personality-based systems are used in education for developing personalized learning experiences [250] that cater to individual learning styles and preferences. In mental health, Personality Computing is used for depression detection tasks in social media [278], and a recent development started a line of research on chatbot-delivered psychotherapy for adults with depressive symptoms [172]. Forensic

applications include automatic Personality Recognition to improve deception detection [91] and mixed techniques used for analyzing meetings and conversations of suspected terrorists [205, 268].

There are many applications of personality-aware recommender systems in friend suggestion in social media as well as in product suggestion, where personality information can be used to enhance cold start recommendations [123, 124, 264]. Human-Computer Interaction systems started to employ Computational Personality techniques in the development of avatars and virtual agents, to create more realistic and engaging interactions with users [171, 299]. Then, the diffusion of AI and LLMs boosted the application of Personality Recognition, Perception and Synthesis in chatbots [2]. One of the most successful applications of Personality Computing is in organizational settings for recruiting and talent acquisition. In this field, personality-aware systems are employed to massively assess job candidates [89] from various sources, such as video interviews and text with pictures extracted from CVs. Other applications of Personality Computing include fraud detection systems, for example in the insurance sector and risk assessment [133] and credit scoring to predict repayment behavior [75].

4.2 Threats, Challenges, and Future Directions

Many of the Personality Computing applications described above already have an impact on societies, and also present potential drawbacks with disruptive negative effects. Personality-aware marketing systems have been exploited for political campaigns and influenced voting behavior in different elections [79]. The exploitation of partner matching patterns from dating apps enriched with personality opens scenarios in which personality-aware AI can reach a deep level of intimacy with human subjects [143]. This threat is exacerbated by the fact that Personality Synthesis has already very high performances. Tailoring education to individual personalities has potential, but we need to be careful. If the goal is just student satisfaction, we might sacrifice challenging, high-quality teaching. Furthermore, AI in mental health and forensics requires extreme caution. Errors in detecting depression or delivering AI therapy could be disastrous. In these situations, AI can develop a very close, personal connection with people, making accuracy crucial. Recommendation systems may also have unintended consequences. Research suggests that users often add people to their social networks who are similar to themselves. Enhancing this pattern with personality-aware friends recommendation systems could potentially boost the formation of echo chambers [262]. Another potential application with heavy consequences is personality-aware credit scoring. Although it is possible to build systems that output transparent decisions about credit assignments [291], personality has to do with persistent patterns of behavior, so decisions that weight personality too much yield to a high risk of leaving certain types of people without credit, creating social marginalization.

The rise of research trends related to LLMs (Machine Personality, Personality Hacking, and Personality Safety) have the potential to reshape the field of Personality Computing, and this could also have an impact on Personality Psychology. From an interdisciplinary perspective, Personality Psychology can be useful in Personality Safety to study artificial intimacy from the human side, while the expertise of psychologists can be useful to create assessments specific for LLMs [257]. To ensure the responsible growth of personality computing, researchers must proactively address upcoming challenges. We suggest three key areas of focus to help minimize the negative impacts of these technologies:

- (1) New tasks that meet the requirements of new regulations and address Personality Safety. For example, Personality Synthesis can be used for the generation of synthetic, anonymous data annotated with personality; Personality Recognition techniques can be used for automatically altering digital footprints to mask personality cues; while Personality Perception can be integrated by explainable AI to provide understandable reasons for personality predictions.

- (2) Collaborations with new research communities. Historically, the community working in Personality Computing had many relationships with the communities working in Personality Psychology, Natural Language Processing, Affective Computing and Computer Vision to develop better systems. We suggest that it is time to interact with communities working in Cybersecurity, Computational Social Sciences, and Computational History, for example, organizing workshops, to understand the social impact that these systems will have in the future, and find methods to mitigate the negative impacts.
- (3) Standardizing evaluation metrics and benchmarks. We advocate for the use of correlation coefficients as the standard metric for all Personality Computing tasks. The field has largely shifted from classification metrics, such as accuracy and F1-score, to correlations, which better align with regression-based trait score predictions. Conversely, outdated practices like artificial dichotomization (e.g., median splits) should be discouraged. Furthermore, hosting benchmarks and evaluation protocols on platforms like GitHub, Kaggle, or Hugging Face will significantly enhance research replicability and comparability.

We tend to humanize Artificial Intelligence. The ability of LLMs to synthesize personality and emotions makes the human factor even more vulnerable in terms of privacy and cybersecurity. In order to properly formulate AI to human interaction, and protect end users from potential threats, a number of parameters have to be taken into account in terms of both technical and personality fronts. In general, we hope that new Personality Computing tasks and future research collaborations between communities will go in the direction of preventing machines from carrying out social engineering strategies on a large scale.

Author Contributions

FC: Conceptualization, Supervision, Review and Editing; AK: Resources and materials, Supervision, Review and Editing; MD: Resources and materials, Review and Editing; DS: Review and Editing; VF: Review and Editing; VM: Review and Editing; GS: Review and Editing, Funding Acquisition; AV: Review and Editing; MK: Review and Editing; BL: Supervision, Review and Editing.

References

- [1] Sibel Adali and Jennifer Golbeck. 2014. Predicting personality with social behavior: a comparative study. *Social Network Analysis and Mining* 4, 159 (2014), 1–20.
- [2] Tarek Ait Baha, Mohamed El Hajji, Youssef Es-Saady, and Hammou Fadili. 2023. The power of personalization: A systematic review of personality-adaptive chatbots. *SN Computer Science* 4, 5 (2023), 661.
- [3] Mehdi Akbari, Mohammad Seydavi, Marcantonio M. Spada, Shahram Mohammadkhani, Shiva Jamshidi, Alireza Jamaloo, and Fatemeh Ayatmehr. 2021. The big five personality traits and online gaming: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions* 10, 3 (2021), 611–625.
- [4] Noura Al Moubayed, Yolanda Vazquez-Alvarez, Alex McKay, and Alessandro Vinciarelli. 2014. Face-based automatic personality perception. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 1153–1156 pages.
- [5] Firoj Alam and Giuseppe Riccardi. 2013. Comparative study of speaker personality traits recognition in conversational and broadcast news speech. *INTERSPEECH* (2013), 2851–2855 pages.
- [6] Firoj Alam and Giuseppe Riccardi. 2014. Fusion of acoustic, linguistic and psycholinguistic features for speaker personality traits recognition. In *Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*. 955–959 pages.
- [7] Firoj Alam, Evgeny A. Stepanov, and Giuseppe Riccardi. 2013. Personality traits recognition on social network-facebook. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 6–9 pages.
- [8] Gordon W. Allport and Henry S. Odbert. 1936. Trait-names: A psycho-lexical study. *Psychological Monographs* 47, 1 (1936), i.
- [9] Aamena Alshamsi, Fabio Pianesi, Bruno Lepri, Alex Pentland, and Iyad Rahwan. 2015. Beyond contagion: Reality mining reveals complex patterns of social influence. *PLoS One* 10, 8 (2015), e0135740.
- [10] Oya Aran and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2013. Cross-domain personality prediction: from video blogs to small group meetings. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM on International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. 127–130 pages.

- [11] Shlomo Argamon, Moshe Koppel, James W. Pennebaker, and Jonathan Schler. 2009. Automatically profiling the author of an anonymous text. *Communications of the ACM* 52, 2 (2009), 119–123.
- [12] Junaid Asghar, Saima Akbar, Muhammad Zubair Asghar, Bashir Ahmad, Mabrook S. Al-Rakhami, and Abdu Gumaie. 2021. Detection and classification of psychopathic personality trait from social media text using deep learning model. *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine* 2021, 1 (2021), 1–10.
- [13] Süleyman Aslan and Uğur Güdükbay. 2019. Multimodal video-based apparent personality recognition using long short-term memory and convolutional neural networks. *ArXiv abs/1911.00381* (2019), 1–10.
- [14] Danny Azucar, Davide Marengo, and Michele Settanni. 2018. Predicting the big 5 personality traits from digital footprints on social media: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences* 124 (2018), 150–159.
- [15] S. C. Matz B. Freiberg. 2023. Founder personality and entrepreneurial outcomes: A large-scale field study of technology startups. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120, 19 (2023), e2215829120.
- [16] Yoram Bachrach, Michal Kosinski, Thore Graepel, Pushmeet Kohli, and David Stillwell. 2012. Personality and patterns of Facebook usage. In *Proceedings of the 4th annual ACM Web Science Conference*. 24–32 pages.
- [17] Shuotian Bai, Bibo Hao, Ang Li, Sha Yuan, Rui Gao, and Tingshao Zhu. 2013. Predicting big five personality traits of microblog users. In *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Joint Conferences on Web Intelligence (WI) and Intelligent Agent Technologies*. IEEE, 501–508.
- [18] Shuotian Bai, Sha Yuan, Bibo Hao, and Tingshao Zhu. 2014. Predicting personality traits of microblog users. *Web Intelligence and Agent Systems: An International Journal* 12, 3 (2014), 249–265.
- [19] BA Balgiu. 2018. The psychometric properties of the big five inventory-10 (BFI-10) including correlations with subjective and psychological well-being. *Global Journal of Psychology Research: New Trends and Issues* 8, 2 (2018), 61–69.
- [20] Valentin Barriere, João Sedoc, Shabnam Tafreshi, and Salvatore Giorgi. 2023. Findings of WASSA 2023 shared task on empathy, emotion and personality detection in conversation and reactions to news articles. In *Proceedings of the 13th Workshop on Computational Approaches to Subjectivity, Sentiment, and Social Media Analysis*. 511–525.
- [21] Valentin Barriere, Shabnam Tafreshi, João Sedoc, and Sawsan Alqahtani. 2022. WASSA 2022 shared task: Predicting empathy, emotion and personality in reaction to news stories. In *Proceedings of the 12th Workshop on Computational Approaches to Subjectivity, Sentiment and Social Media Analysis*. 214–227.
- [22] Ligia Batrinca, Bruno Lepri, Nadia Mana, and Fabio Pianesi. 2012. Multimodal recognition of personality traits in human-computer collaborative tasks. In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. 39–46 pages.
- [23] Ligia Batrinca, Nadia Mana, Bruno Lepri, Nicu Sebe, and Fabio Pianesi. 2016. Multimodal personality recognition in collaborative goal-oriented tasks. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* 18, 4 (2016), 659–673.
- [24] Ligia Maria Batrinca, Nadia Mana, Bruno Lepri, Fabio Pianesi, and Nicu Sebe. 2011. Please, tell me about yourself: Automatic personality assessment using short self-presentations. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces*. ACM, 255–262.
- [25] Herbert Bay, Tinne Tuytelaars, and Luc Van Gool. 2006. Surf: Speeded up robust features. In *Proceedings of the Computer Vision–ECCV 2006*. Springer, 404–417.
- [26] Pranav Bhandari, Usman Naseem, Amitava Datta, Nicolas Fay, and Mehwish Nasim. 2025. Evaluating personality traits in large language models: Insights from psychological questionnaires. In *Companion Proceedings of the ACM on Web Conference 2025*. 868–872.
- [27] Srilakshmi Bharadwaj, Srinidhi Sridhar, Rahul Choudhary, and Ramamoorthy Srinath. 2018. Persona traits identification based on Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)-a text classification approach. In *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communications and Informatics*. IEEE, 1076–1082.
- [28] Harshit Bhardwaj, Pradeep Tomar, Aditi Sakalle, Arpit Bhardwaj, Rishi Asthana, and Ankit Vidyarthi. 2023. EEG based personality prediction using genetic programming. *Asian Journal of Control* 25, 5 (2023), 3330–3342.
- [29] Adriana Bianchi and James G. Phillips. 2005. Psychological predictors of problem mobile phone use. *Cyberpsychology and Behavior* 8, 1 (2005), 39–51.
- [30] Joan-Isaac Biel, Oya Aran, and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2011. You are known by how you vlog: Personality impressions and nonverbal behavior in youtube. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 446–449.
- [31] Joan-Isaac Biel and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2012. The youtube lens: Crowdsourced personality impressions and audiovisual analysis of vlogs. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* 15, 1 (2012), 41–55.
- [32] Joan-Isaac Biel, Lucía Teijeiro-Mosquera, and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2012. Facetube: Predicting personality from facial expressions of emotion in online conversational video. In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. 53–56.
- [33] Joan-Isaac Biel, Vagia Tsiminaki, John Dines, and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2013. Hi youtube! personality impressions and verbal content in social video. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. 119–126.

- [34] Wiebke Bleidorn and Christopher James Hopwood. 2019. Using machine learning to advance personality assessment and theory. *Personality and Social Psychology Review* 23, 2 (2019), 190–203.
- [35] Michael H. Bond, Hiroaki Nakazato, and Daisuke Shiraishi. 1975. Universality and distinctiveness in dimensions of Japanese person perception. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 6, 3 (1975), 346–357.
- [36] Ryan L. Boyd, Ashwini Ashokkumar, Sarah Seraj, and James W. Pennebaker. 2022. The development and psychometric properties of LIWC-22. *Austin, TX: University of Texas at Austin* 10 (2022), 1–47.
- [37] Gregory Boyle and Edward Helmes. 2009. *Methods of Personality Assessment* (126 ed.). Vol. 110. Cambridge University Press, 110–126.
- [38] Gregory J. Boyle. 1995. Myers-briggs type indicator (MBTI): Some psychometric limitations. *Australian Psychologist* 30, 1 (1995), 71–74.
- [39] Willem-Paul Brinkman and Nick Fine. 2005. Towards customized emotional design: an explorative study of user personality and user interface skin preferences. In *Proceedings of the 2005 Annual Conference on European Association of Cognitive Ergonomics*. 107–114.
- [40] Iván Cantador, Ignacio Fernández-Tobías, Alejandro Bellogín, Michal Kosinski, and David Stillwell. 2013. Relating personality types with user preferences in multiple entertainment domains. In *Proceedings of the UMAP Workshops*.
- [41] Gustavo Carlo, George P. Knight, Scott C. Roesch, Deanna Opal, and Alexandra Davis. 2014. Personality across cultures: A critical analysis of Big Five research and current directions. (2014), 285–298.
- [42] Heather E. P. Cattell. 2001. The sixteen personality factor (16PF) questionnaire. In *Proceedings of the Understanding Psychological Assessment*. Springer, 187–215.
- [43] Fabio Celli, Elia Bruni, and Bruno Lepri. 2014. Automatic personality and interaction style recognition from facebook profile pictures. In *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. ACM, 1101–1104.
- [44] Fabio Celli and Bruno Lepri. 2018. Is big five better than MBTI? A personality computing challenge using Twitter data. *Computational Linguistics CLiC-it 2018* (2018), 93.
- [45] Fabio Celli, Bruno Lepri, Joan-Isaac Biel, Daniel Gatica-Perez, Giuseppe Riccardi, and Fabio Pianesi. 2014. The workshop on computational personality recognition 2014. In *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. ACM, 1245–1246.
- [46] Fabio Celli, Pietro Zani Massani, and Bruno Lepri. 2017. Profilio: Psychometric profiling to boost social media advertising. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 546–550.
- [47] Fabio Celli, Fabio Pianesi, David Stillwell, and Michal Kosinski. 2013. Workshop on computational personality recognition: Shared task. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 2–5.
- [48] Fabio Celli and Luca Rossi. 2012. The role of emotional stability in Twitter conversations. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Semantic Analysis in Social Media*. 10–17.
- [49] Shristi Chaudhary, Ritu Singh, Syed Tausif Hasan, and Ms Inderpreet Kaur. 2013. A comparative study of different classifiers for myers-brigg personality prediction model. *Linguistic Analysis* 21 (2013).
- [50] Tianqi Chen and Carlos Guestrin. 2016. XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 785–794.
- [51] Fanny M. Cheung, Fons J. R. van de Vijver, and Frederick T. L. Leong. 2011. Toward a new approach to the study of personality in culture. *American Psychologist* 66, 7 (2011), 593.
- [52] Gokul Chittaranjan, Jan Blom, and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2011. Who’s who with big-five: Analyzing and classifying personality traits with smartphones. In *Proceedings of the 2011 15th Annual International Symposium on Wearable Computers*. IEEE, 29–36.
- [53] Gokul Chittaranjan, Jan Blom, and Daniel Gatica-Perez. 2013. Mining large-scale smartphone data for personality studies. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing* 17, 3 (2013), 433–450.
- [54] Hans Christian, Derwin Suhartono, Andry Chowanda, and Kamal Z. Zamli. 2021. Text based personality prediction from multiple social media data sources using pre-trained language model and model averaging. *Journal of Big Data* 8, 1 (2021), 68.
- [55] Max Coltheart. 1981. The MRC psycholinguistic database. *The Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology Section A* 33, 4 (1981), 497–505.
- [56] Brian S. Connelly and Deniz S. Ones. 2010. An other perspective on personality: meta-analytic integration of observers’ accuracy and predictive validity. *Psychological bulletin* 136, 6 (2010), 1092.
- [57] Stanley Coopersmith. 1959. A method for determining types of self-esteem. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology* 59, 1 (1959), 87.
- [58] Glen Coppersmith, Mark Dredze, and Craig Harman. 2014. Quantifying mental health signals in Twitter. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Computational Linguistics and Clinical Psychology: From Linguistic Signal to Clinical Reality*. 51–60.
- [59] Wrzus Cornelia and Mehl Matthias R. 2015. Lab and/or field? Measuring personality processes and their social consequences. *European Journal of Personality* 29 (2015), 250–271.

- [60] Corinna Cortes and Vladimir Vapnik. 1995. Support-vector networks. *Machine Learning* 20, 3 (1995), 273–297.
- [61] Paul T. Costa and Robert R. McCrae. 1992. Normal personality assessment in clinical practice: The NEO Personality Inventory. *Psychological Assessment* 4, 1 (1992), 5.
- [62] Paul T. Costa and Robert R. McCrae. 2008. The revised NEO personality inventory (NEO-PI-R). *The SAGE Handbook of Personality Theory and Assessment* 2 (2008), 179–198.
- [63] Marcus Credé, Peter Harms, Sarah Niehorster, and Andrea Gaye-Valentine. 2012. An evaluation of the consequences of using short measures of the Big Five personality traits. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 102, 4 (2012), 874.
- [64] Douglas P. Crowne and David Marlowe. 1960. A new scale of social desirability independent of psychopathology. *Journal of Consulting Psychology* 24, 4 (1960), 349–354.
- [65] Yves-Alexandre de Montjoye, Jordi Quoidbach, Florent Robic, and Alex Sandy Pentland. 2013. Predicting personality using novel mobile phone-based metrics. In *Proceedings of the Social Computing, Behavioral-Cultural Modeling and Prediction*. Springer, 48–55.
- [66] Rodrigo de Oliveira, Alexandros Karatzoglou, Pedro Concejero Cerezo, Ana Armenta Lopez de Vicuña, and Nuria Oliver. 2011. Towards a psychographic user model from mobile phone usage. In *Proceedings of the Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 2191–2196.
- [67] Jean-Marc Dewaele and Adrian Furnham. 2000. Personality and speech production: A pilot study of second language learners. *Personality and Individual Differences* 28, 2 (2000), 355–365.
- [68] Sahraoui Dhelim, Nyothiri Aung, Mohammed Amine Bouras, Huansheng Ning, and Erik Cambria. 2022. A survey on personality-aware recommendation systems. *Artificial Intelligence Review* 55, 3 (2022), 2409–2454.
- [69] John M. Digman. 1990. Personality structure: Emergence of the five-factor model. *Annual Review of Psychology* 41, 1 (1990), 417–440.
- [70] M. Brent Donnellan, Rand D. Conger, and Chalandra M. Bryant. 2004. The big five and enduring marriages. *Journal of Research in Personality* 38, 5 (2004), 481–504.
- [71] M. Brent Donnellan, Frederick L. Oswald, Brendan M. Baird, and Richard E. Lucas. 2006. The mini-IPIP scales: Tiny-yet-effective measures of the big five factors of personality. *Psychological Assessment* 18, 2 (2006), 192.
- [72] Kamal El-Demerdash, Reda A. El-Khoribi, Mahmoud A. Ismail Shoman, and Sherif Abdou. 2022. Deep learning based fusion strategies for personality prediction. *Egyptian Informatics Journal* 23, 1 (2022), 47–53.
- [73] Frank Enos, Stefan Benus, Robin L. Cautin, Martin Graciarena, Julia Hirschberg, and Elizabeth Shriberg. 2006. Personality factors in human deception detection: Comparing human to machine performance. *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association* 2 (2006), 813 – 816.
- [74] Izel Ergu, Zerrin Işık, and İsmail Yankayış. 2019. Predicting personality with twitter data and machine learning models. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Innovations in Intelligent Systems and Applications Conference*. IEEE, 1–5.
- [75] Adnan Veysel Ertemel and Gökhan Çaylak. 2021. The effect of personality traits on credit score using Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality types. In *Eurasian Business and Economics Perspectives: Proceedings of the 32nd Eurasia Business and Economics Society Conference*. Springer, 185–199.
- [76] Dominique Estival, Tanja Gaustad, Son Bao Pham, Will Radford, and Ben Hutchinson. 2007. Author profiling for English emails. In *Proceedings of the 10th Conference of the Pacific Association for Computational Linguistics*. 263–272.
- [77] Morgane Evin, Antonio Hidalgo-Munoz, Adolphe James Béquet, Fabien Moreau, Hélène Tattégain, Catherine Berthelon, Alexandra Fort, and Christophe Jallais. 2022. Personality trait prediction by machine learning using physiological data and driving behavior. *Machine Learning with Applications* 9 (2022), 100353.
- [78] Florian Eyben, Martin Wöllmer, and Björn Schuller. 2010. Opensmile: The munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 1459–1462.
- [79] Filipe Falcão, Bárbara Sousa, Daniela S. M. Pereira, Renato Andrade, Pedro Moreira, Anna Quialheiro, Carlos Jalali, and Patrício Costa. 2023. We vote for the person, not the policies: a systematic review on how personality traits influence voting behaviour. *Discover Psychology* 3, 1 (2023), 1.
- [80] Golnoosh Farnadi, Geetha Sitaraman, Mehrdad Rohani, Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, Marie-Francine Moens, Sergio Davalos, and Martine De Cock. 2014. How are you doing?: Emotions and personality in Facebook. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Emotions and Personality in Personalized Services; workshop at the 22nd Conference on User Modelling, Adaptation and Personalization*. 45–56.
- [81] Golnoosh Farnadi, Geetha Sitaraman, Shanu Sushmita, Fabio Celli, Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, Sergio Davalos, Marie-Francine Moens, and Martine De Cock. 2016. Computational personality recognition in social media. *User Modeling and User-adapted Interaction* 26 (2016), 109–142.
- [82] Golnoosh Farnadi, Shanu Sushmita, Geetha Sitaraman, Nhat Ton, Martine De Cock, and Sergio Davalos. 2014. A multivariate regression approach to personality impression recognition of vloggers. In *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM Multi Media on Workshop on Computational Personality Recognition*. 1–6.
- [83] Golnoosh Farnadi, Susana Zoghbi, Marie-Francine Moens, and Martine De Cock. 2013. Recognising personality traits using facebook status updates. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 14–18.

- [84] L.W. Ferguson. 1952. *Personality Measurement*. McGraw-Hill.
- [85] Bruce Ferwerda, Markus Schedl, and Marko Tkalcić. 2015. Predicting personality traits with instagram pictures. In *Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Emotions and Personality in Personalized Systems 2015*. 7–10.
- [86] Bruce Ferwerda, Markus Schedl, and Marko Tkalcić. 2016. Using instagram picture features to predict users' personality. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Multimedia Modeling*. Springer, 850–861.
- [87] Bruce Ferwerda and Marko Tkalcić. 2018. Predicting users' personality from Instagram pictures: using visual and/or content features?. In *Proceedings of the 26th Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*. 157–161.
- [88] Bruce Ferwerda and Marko Tkalcić. 2018. You are what you post: What the content of Instagram pictures tells about users' personality. In *Proceedings of the 23rd International on Intelligent User Interfaces*. CEUR-WS.
- [89] Alan Funder et al. 2006. For some, online persona undermines a resume. *The New York Times* 11 (2006).
- [90] William Fleeson. 2001. Toward a structure-and process-integrated view of personality: Traits as density distributions of states. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 80, 6 (2001), 1011.
- [91] Tommaso Fornaciari, Fabio Celli, and Massimo Poesio. 2013. The effect of personality type on deceptive communication style. In *Proceedings of the 2013 European Intelligence and Security Informatics Conference*. IEEE, 1–6.
- [92] Yoav Freund and Robert E. Schapire. 1997. A decision-theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* 55 (1997), 119–139.
- [93] David C. Funder. 2001. Personality. *Annual Review of Psychology* 52, 3 (2001), 197–221.
- [94] David C. Funder. 2006. Towards a resolution of the personality triad: Persons, situations, and behaviors. *Journal of Research in Personality* 40 (2006), 21–34.
- [95] Christopher M. Gallagher, Brent A. Stevener, Andrew Samo, and Samuel T. McAbee. 2023. A short measure of the big five aspects: Development and validation of the BFAS-40. *Journal of Personality Assessment* 105, 6 (2023), 719–732.
- [96] Peter Zhuowei Gan, Arcot Sowmya, and Gelareh Mohammadi. 2022. Zero-shot personality perception from facial images. In *Proceedings of the Australasian Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Springer, 43–56.
- [97] Adithya V. Ganesan, Yash Kumar Lal, August Nilsson, and H Schwartz. 2023. Systematic evaluation of GPT-3 for zero-shot personality estimation. In *Proceedings of the 13th Workshop on Computational Approaches to Subjectivity, Sentiment, and Social Media Analysis*. 390–400.
- [98] Salvatore Giorgi, João Sedoc, Valentin Barriere, and Shabnam Tafreshi. 2024. Findings of wassa 2024 shared task on empathy and personality detection in interactions. In *Proceedings of the 14th Workshop on Computational Approaches to Subjectivity, Sentiment, and Social Media Analysis*. 369–379.
- [99] Matej Gjurković, Vanja Mladen Karan, Iva Vukojević, Mihaela Bošnjak, and Jan Snajder. 2021. PANDORA talks: Personality and demographics on reddit. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Social Media*. Lun-Wei Ku and Cheng-Te Li (Eds.), Association for Computational Linguistics, Online, 138–152. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.socialnlp-1.12>
- [100] Joe J. Gladstone, Sandra C. Matz, and Alain Lemaire. 2019. Can psychological traits be inferred from spending? Evidence from transaction data. *Psychological Science* 30, 7 (2019), 1087–1096.
- [101] Jennifer Golbeck. 2016. Predicting personality from social media text. *AIS Transactions on Replication Research* 2, 1 (2016), 2.
- [102] Jennifer Golbeck, Cristina Robles, Michon Edmondson, and Karen Turner. 2011. Predicting personality from twitter. In *Proceedings of the 2011 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Privacy, Security, Risk and Trust and 2011 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Social Computing*. IEEE, 149–156.
- [103] Jennifer Golbeck, Cristina Robles, and Karen Turner. 2011. Predicting personality with social media. In *Proceedings of the Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 253–262.
- [104] Lewis R. Goldberg. 1982. From ace to zombie: Some explorations in the language of personality. *Advances in Personality Assessment* 1 (1982), 203–234.
- [105] Lewis R. Goldberg. 1990. An alternative “description of personality”: the big-five factor structure. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 59, 6 (1990), 1216.
- [106] Leonard V. Gordon. 1951. Validities of the forced-choice and questionnaire methods of personality measurement. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 35, 6 (1951), 407.
- [107] Louis August Gottschalk and Goldine C Gleser. 1969. *The Measurement of Psychological States Through the Content Analysis of Verbal Behavior*. Univ of California Press.
- [108] Harrison G. Gough. 2012. The california psychological inventory. In *Proceedings of the Testing and Assessment in Counseling Practice*. Routledge, 41–65.
- [109] David T. Graham, John A. Stern, and George Winokur. 1958. Experimental investigation of the specificity of attitude hypothesis in psychosomatic disease. *Psychosomatic Medicine* 20, 6 (1958), 446–457.
- [110] Sharath Chandra Guntuku, Weisi Lin, Jordan Carpenter, Wee Keong Ng, Lyle H. Ungar, and Daniel Preotjuc-Pietro. 2017. Studying personality through the content of posted and liked images on Twitter. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM on Web Science Conference*. 223–227.

- [111] Sharath Chandra Guntuku, Lin Qiu, Sujoy Roy, Weisi Lin, and Vinit Jakhethiya. 2015. Do others perceive you as you want them to? Modeling personality based on selfies. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Affect and Sentiment in Multimedia*. 21–26.
- [112] Sharath Chandra Guntuku, Joey Tianyi Zhou, Sujoy Roy, Weisi Lin, and Ivor W. Tsang. 2016. Who likes what and, why? insights into modeling users' personality based on image 'likes'. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 9, 1 (2016), 130–143.
- [113] Gareth Hagger-Johnson, Vincent Egan, and David Stillwell. 2011. Are social networking profiles reliable indicators of sensational interests? *Journal of Research in Personality* 45, 1 (2011), 71–76.
- [114] Pietter Haizel, Grace Vernanda, Keyzia Alexandra Wawolangi, and Novita Hanafiah. 2021. Personality assessment video game based on the five-factor model. *Procedia Computer Science* 179 (2021), 566–573.
- [115] Noptovius Halimawan, Derwin Suhartono, Aryo Pradipta Gema, and Rezki Yunanda. 2022. BERT and ULMFiT ensemble for personality prediction from Indonesian social media text. In *Proceedings of the 2022 International Symposium on Information Technology and Digital Innovation*. IEEE, 156–161.
- [116] Yuval Noah Harari. 2024. *Nexus: A Brief History of Information Networks From the Stone Age to AI*. Signal.
- [117] John Hartley, Conor Brian Hamill, Dale Seddon, Devesh Batra, Ramin Okhrati, and Raad Khraishi. 2025. How personality traits shape llm risk-taking behaviour. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. 21068–21092.
- [118] Thomas F Heston and Justin Gillette. 2025. Do large language models have a personality? A psychometric evaluation with implications for clinical medicine and mental health AI. *MedRxiv* (2025), 2025–03.
- [119] Joanne Hinds and Adam N. Joinson. 2024. Digital data and personality: A systematic review and meta-analysis of human perception and computer prediction. *Psychological Bulletin* 150, 6 (2024), 727.
- [120] Robert Hogan and Joyce Hogan. 1995. Hogan personality inventory. *Journal of Applied Psychology* (1995).
- [121] Linmei Hu, Hongyu He, Duokang Wang, Ziwang Zhao, Yingxia Shao, and Liqiang Nie. 2024. LLM vs small model? Large language model based text augmentation enhanced personality detection model. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. 18234–18242.
- [122] Rong Hu and Pearl Pu. 2009. Acceptance issues of personality-based recommender systems. In *Proceedings of the third ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*. 221–224.
- [123] Rong Hu and Pearl Pu. 2010. Using personality information in collaborative filtering for new users. *Recommender Systems and the Social Web* 17 (2010), 60–70.
- [124] Rong Hu and Pearl Pu. 2011. Enhancing collaborative filtering systems with personality information. In *Proceedings of the 5th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*. 197–204.
- [125] Jen-tse Huang, Wenxuan Wang, Eric John Li, Man Ho Lam, Shujie Ren, Youliang Yuan, Wenxiang Jiao, Zhaopeng Tu, and Michael R. Lyu. 2024. On the humanity of conversational AI: Evaluating the psychological portrayal of LLMs. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Learning Representations*. OpenReview.net.
- [126] Jen-tse Huang, Wenxiang Jiao, Man Ho Lam, Eric John Li, Wenxuan Wang, and Michael Lyu. 2024. On the reliability of psychological scales on large language models. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Yaser Al-Onaizan, Mohit Bansal, and Yun-Nung Chen (Eds.), Association for Computational Linguistics, 6152–6173.
- [127] Muhua Huang. 2025. Designing llm-agents with personalities: A psychometric approach. *Personality Science* 7 (2025).
- [128] Francisco Iacobelli and Aron Culotta. 2013. Too neurotic, not too friendly: Structured personality classification on textual data. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 19–22.
- [129] Francisco Iacobelli, Alastair J. Gill, Scott Nowson, and Jon Oberlander. 2011. Large scale personality classification of bloggers. In *Proceedings of the Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction*. Springer, 568–577.
- [130] Alexei V. Ivanov, Giuseppe Riccardi, Adam J. Sporka, and Jakub Franc. 2011. Recognition of personality traits from human spoken conversations. In *Proceedings of the Interspeech*. 1549–1552.
- [131] Chris J. Jackson and Leslie J. Francis. 1998. Interpreting the correlation between neuroticism and lie scale scores. *Personality and Individual Differences* 26, 1 (1998), 59–63.
- [132] Julio C. S. Jacques Junior, Yağmur Güçlütürk, Marc Pérez, Umüt Güçlü, Carlos Andujar, Xavier Baró, Hugo Jair Escalante, Isabelle Guyon, Marcel A. J. van Gerven, Rob van Lier, et al. 2022. First impressions: A survey on vision-based apparent personality trait analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 13, 1 (2022), 75–95.
- [133] Nahariah Jaffar, Hasnah Haron, Takiyah Mohd Iskandar, and Arfah Salleh. 2011. Fraud risk assessment and detection of fraud: the moderating effect of personality. *International Journal of Business and Management* 6, 7 (2011), 40.
- [134] Madhura Jayaratne and Buddhi Jayatilleke. 2020. Predicting personality using answers to open-ended interview questions. *IEEE Access* 8 (2020), 115345–115355.
- [135] Guangyuan Jiang, Manjie Xu, Song-Chun Zhu, Wenjuan Han, Chi Zhang, and Yixin Zhu. 2023. Evaluating and inducing personality in pre-trained language models. In *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*. Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, Article 466, 22 pages.

- [136] Hang Jiang, Xiajie Zhang, Xubo Cao, Cynthia Breazeal, Deb Roy, and Jad Kabbara. 2024. PersonaLLM: Investigating the ability of large language models to express personality traits. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Kevin Duh, Helena Gomez, and Steven Bethard (Eds.), Association for Computational Linguistics, Mexico City, Mexico, 3605–3627.
- [137] Hang Jiang, Xiajie Zhang, Xubo Cao, Cynthia Breazeal, Deb Roy, and Jad Kabbara. 2024. PersonaLLM: Investigating the ability of large language models to express personality traits. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. 3605–3627.
- [138] Liying Jiao, Chang-Jin Li, Zhen Chen, Hengbin Xu, and Yan Xu. 2025. When AI “possesses” personality: Roles of good and evil personalities influence moral judgment in large language models. *Acta Psychologica Sinica* (2025).
- [139] Oliver P. John. 1990. The “big five” factor taxonomy: Dimensions of personality in the natural language and in questionnaires. *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research* (1990).
- [140] Oliver P. John, Richard W. Robins, and Lawrence A. Pervin. 2010. *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research*. Guilford Press.
- [141] John A. Johnson. 2014. Measuring thirty facets of the Five Factor Model with a 120-item public domain inventory: Development of the IPIP-NEO-120. *Journal of Research in Personality* 51 (2014), 78–89.
- [142] Daniel N. Jones and Delroy L. Paulhus. 2014. Introducing the short dark triad (SD3): A brief measure of dark personality traits. *Assessment* 21, 1 (2014), 28–41.
- [143] Mirabelle Jones, Nastasia Griffioen, Christina Neumayer, and Irina Shklovski. 2025. Artificial intimacy: Exploring normativity and personalization through fine-tuning LLM chatbots. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 1–16.
- [144] Carl G. Jung. 1971. Personality types. *The Portable Jung*. 178–272.
- [145] Alexander Kachur, Evgeny Osin, Denis Davydov, Konstantin Shutilov, and Alexey Novokshonov. 2020. Assessing the big five personality traits using real-life static facial images. *Scientific Reports* 10, 1 (2020), 8487.
- [146] Kyriaki Kalimeri, Bruno Lepri, and Fabio Pianesi. 2010. Causal-modelling of personality traits: extraversion and locus of control. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Social Signal Processing*. 41–46.
- [147] Kyriaki Kalimeri, Bruno Lepri, and Fabio Pianesi. 2013. Going beyond traits: Multimodal classification of personality states in the wild. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM on International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. ACM, 27–34.
- [148] Onno Kampman, Elham J. Barezi, Dario Bertero, and Pascale Fung. 2018. Investigating audio, visual, and text fusion methods for end-to-end automatic personality prediction. In *Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers)*. 606–611.
- [149] Arvid Karsvall. 2002. Personality preferences in graphical interface design. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*. 217–218.
- [150] KMGS Karunarathna, MPRIR Silva, and RAHM Rupasingha. 2023. Ensemble learning approach for identifying personality traits based on individuals’ behavior. *EDITORIAL NOTE* (2023), 107.
- [151] Vishal Kaushal and Manasi Patwardhan. 2018. Emerging trends in personality identification using online social networks—a literature survey. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data* 12, 2 (2018), 1–30.
- [152] Amirmohammad Kazameini, Samin Fatehi, Yash Mehta, Sauleh Eetemadi, and Erik Cambria. 2020. Personality trait detection using bagged svm over bert word embedding ensembles. arXiv:2010.01309. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.01309>
- [153] Edbert Ivan Sebastian Kelvin and Suhartono Derwin. 2023. Utilizing IndoBERT in predicting personality from twitter posts using bahasa indonesia. *ICIC Express Letters* 17, 01 (2023), 123.
- [154] Maurice Kendall and Jean D. Gibbons. 1990. *Rank Correlation Methods*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [155] Katia Lida Kermanidis. 2012. Mining authors’ personality traits from modern greek spontaneous text. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Corpora for Research on Emotion Sentiment and Social Signals, in Conjunction with LREC*. Citeseer, 90–93.
- [156] Margaret L. Kern, Paul X. McCarthy, Deepanjan Chakrabarty, and Marian-Andrei Rizoiu. 2019. Social media-predicted personality traits and values can help match people to their ideal jobs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 16 (2019), 26459–26464.
- [157] Lawrence J. Klinkert, Steph Buongiorno, and Corey Clark. 2024. Evaluating the efficacy of LLMs to emulate realistic human personalities. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment*, Vol. 20. 65–75.
- [158] Michal Kosinski, Yoram Bachrach, Pushmeet Kohli, David Stillwell, and Thore Graepel. 2014. Manifestations of user personality in website choice and behaviour on online social networks. *Machine Learning* 95, 3 (2014), 357–380.
- [159] Michal Kosinski, Sandra C. Matz, Samuel D. Gosling, Vesselin Popov, and David Stillwell. 2015. Facebook as a research tool for the social sciences: Opportunities, challenges, ethical considerations, and practical guidelines. *American Psychologist* 70, 6 (2015), 543.

- [160] Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, and Thore Graepel. 2013. Private traits and attributes are predictable from digital records of human behavior. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, 15 (2013), 5802–5805.
- [161] Ivar Krumpal. 2013. Determinants of social desirability bias in sensitive surveys: a literature review. *Quality and Quantity* 47, 4 (2013), 2025–2047.
- [162] Akshi Kumar, Rohit Beniwal, and Dipika Jain. 2023. Personality detection using kernel-based ensemble model for leveraging social psychology in online networks. *ACM Transactions on Asian and Low-Resource Language Information Processing* 22, 5 (2023), 1–20.
- [163] Aditi V. Kunte and Suja Panicker. 2019. Using textual data for personality prediction: A machine learning approach. In *Proceedings of the 2019 4th International Conference on Information Systems and Computer Networks*. IEEE, 529–533.
- [164] Vasileios Lampos, Nikolaos Aletras, Daniel Preotiuc-Pietro, and Trevor Cohn. 2014. Predicting and characterising user impact on Twitter. In *Proceedings of the 14th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. 405–413.
- [165] Kibeom Lee and Michael C. Ashton. 2018. Psychometric properties of the HEXACO-100. *Assessment* 25, 5 (2018), 543–556.
- [166] Bruno Lepri, Nadia Mana, Alessandro Cappelletti, Fabio Pianesi, and Massimo Zancanaro. 2009. Modeling the personality of participants during group interactions. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation, and Personalization*. Springer, 114–125.
- [167] Bruno Lepri, Ramanathan Subramanian, Kyriaki Kalimeri, Jacopo Staiano, Fabio Pianesi, and Nicu Sebe. 2010. Employing social gaze and speaking activity for automatic determination of the extraversion trait. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces and the Workshop on Machine Learning for Multimodal Interaction*. ACM, 7.
- [168] Bruno Lepri, Ramanathan Subramanian, Kyriaki Kalimeri, Jacopo Staiano, Fabio Pianesi, and Nicu Sebe. 2012. Connecting meeting behavior with extraversion—A systematic study. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 3, 4 (2012), 443–455.
- [169] Wenyu Li, Xin Hu, Xuefei Long, Lilu Tang, Jingjing Chen, Fei Wang, and Dan Zhang. 2020. EEG responses to emotional videos can quantitatively predict big-five personality traits. *Neurocomputing* 415 (2020), 368–381.
- [170] Wenkai Li, Jiarui Liu, Andy Liu, Xuhui Zhou, Mona Diab, and Maarten Sap. 2025. Big5-chat: Shaping llm personalities through training on human-grounded data. In *Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. 20434–20471.
- [171] Tze Wei Liew and Su-Mae Tan. 2016. Virtual agents with personality: Adaptation of learner-agent personality in a virtual learning environment. In *Proceedings of the 2016 11th International Conference on Digital Information Management*. IEEE, 157–162.
- [172] Shi Min Lim, Chyi Wey Claudine Shiau, Ling Jie Cheng, and Ying Lau. 2022. Chatbot-delivered psychotherapy for adults with depressive and anxiety symptoms: a systematic review and meta-regression. *Behavior Therapy* 53, 2 (2022), 334–347.
- [173] P. H. Lodhi, Savita Deo, and Vivek M. Belhekar. 2002. The five-factor model of personality: Measurement and correlates in the Indian context. *The Five-Factor Model of Personality Across Cultures* (2002), 227–248.
- [174] David Lowe. 2004. Distinctive image features from scale-invariant keypoints. *International Journal of Computer Vision* 60, 2 (2004).
- [175] Kim Luyckx and Walter Daelemans. 2008. Personae: A corpus for author and personality prediction from text. In *Proceedings of the LREC*.
- [176] François Mairesse and Marilyn Walker. 2006. Automatic recognition of personality in conversation. In *Proceedings of the Human Language Technology Conference of the NAACL, Companion Volume: Short Papers*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 85–88.
- [177] François Mairesse and Marilyn Walker. 2007. PERSONAGE: Personality generation for dialogue. In *Proceedings of the 45th Annual Meeting of the Association of Computational Linguistics*. 496–503.
- [178] François Mairesse, Marilyn Walker, et al. 2006. Words mark the nerds: Computational models of personality recognition through language. In *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*.
- [179] François Mairesse, Marilyn A. Walker, Matthias R. Mehl, and Roger K. Moore. 2007. Using linguistic cues for the automatic recognition of personality in conversation and text. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 30 (2007), 457–500.
- [180] Davide Marengo, Jon D. Elhai, and Christian Montag. 2023. Predicting big five personality traits from smartphone data: A meta-analysis on the potential of digital phenotyping. *Journal of Personality* 91, 6 (2023), 1410–1424.
- [181] Patrick M. Markey and Charlotte N. Markey. 2009. A brief assessment of the interpersonal circumplex: The IPIP-IPC. *Assessment* 16, 4 (2009), 352–361.
- [182] Sandra C. Matz and Gabriella M. Harari. 2021. Personality–place transactions: Mapping the relationships between big five personality traits, states, and daily places. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 120, 5 (2021), 1367.

- [183] Robert R. McCrae. 1989. Why I advocate the five-factor model: Joint factor analyses of the NEO-PI with other instruments. *Personality Psychology: Recent Trends and Emerging Directions* (1989), 237–245.
- [184] Robert R. McCrae and Paul T. Costa. 2003. *Personality in Adulthood: A Five-Factor Theory Perspective*. Guilford Press.
- [185] Robert R. McCrae and Oliver P. John. 1992. An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications. *Journal of Personality* 60, 2 (1992), 175–215.
- [186] Matthias R. Mehl, Samuel D. Gosling, and James W. Pennebaker. 2006. Personality in its natural habitat: Manifestations and implicit folk theories of personality in daily life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 90, 5 (2006), 862.
- [187] Yash Mehta, Samin Fatehi, Amirmohammad Kazameini, Clemens Stachl, Erik Cambria, and Sauleh Eetemadi. 2020. Bottom-up and top-down: Predicting personality with psycholinguistic and language model features. In *Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*. IEEE, 1184–1189.
- [188] Yash Mehta, Navonil Majumder, Alexander Gelbukh, and Erik Cambria. 2020. Recent trends in deep learning based personality detection. *Artificial Intelligence Review* 53 (2020), 2313–2339.
- [189] Alessandro B. Melchiorre and Markus Schedl. 2020. Personality correlates of music audio preferences for modelling music listeners. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*. 313–317.
- [190] Atsunori Minamikawa and Hiroyuki Yokoyama. 2011. Blog tells what kind of personality you have: egogram estimation from Japanese weblog. In *Proceedings of the ACM 2011 Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work*. 217–220.
- [191] Li Mo, Xiaosan Zhang, Yabin Lin, Zhenghui Yuan, and Zengjun Peng. 2023. Consumers' attitudes towards online advertising: A model of personalization, informativeness, privacy concern and flow experience. *Sustainability* 15, 5 (2023), 4090.
- [192] Saif Mohammad and Svetlana Kiritchenko. 2013. Using nuances of emotion to identify personality. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 27–30.
- [193] Gelareh Mohammadi, Antonio Origlia, Maurizio Filippone, and Alessandro Vinciarelli. 2012. From speech to personality: Mapping voice quality and intonation into personality differences. In *Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 789–792.
- [194] Gelareh Mohammadi and Alessandro Vinciarelli. 2012. Automatic personality perception: Prediction of trait attribution based on prosodic features. *Affective Computing, IEEE Transactions on* 3, 3 (2012), 273–284.
- [195] Gelareh Mohammadi, Alessandro Vinciarelli, and Marcello Mortillaro. 2010. The voice of personality: Mapping nonverbal vocal behavior into trait attributions. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Social Signal Processing*. ACM, 17–20.
- [196] Sara Zannone Gabriella M. Harari A. Aldo Faisal Aleksandar Matic Mohammed Khwaja, Sumer S. Vaid. 2019. Modeling personality vs. modeling personalidad: In-the-wild mobile data analysis in five countries suggests cultural impact on personality models. *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 3 (2019), 1–24. Issue 3.
- [197] Isabel Briggs Myers et al. 1962. *The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator*. Vol. 34. Consulting Psychologists Press Palo Alto, CA.
- [198] Ghinaa Zain Nabiilah and Derwin Suhartono. 2023. Personality classification based on textual data using indonesian pre-trained language model and ensemble majority voting. *Revue d'Intelligence Artificielle* 37, 1 (2023).
- [199] Yair Neuman and Yochai Cohen. 2024. A data set of synthetic utterances for computational personality analysis. *Scientific Data* 11, 1 (2024), 623.
- [200] Thin Nguyen, Dinh Phung, Brett Adams, and Svetha Venkatesh. 2011. Towards discovery of influence and personality traits through social link prediction. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 566–569.
- [201] Dong Nie, Zengda Guan, Bibo Hao, Shuotian Bai, and Tingshao Zhu. 2014. Predicting personality on social media with semi-supervised learning. In *Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Joint Conferences on Web Intelligence (WI) and Intelligent Agent Technologies*. IEEE, 158–165.
- [202] Warren T. Norman. 1963. Personality measurement, faking, and detection: An assessment method for use in personnel selection. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 47, 4 (1963), 225.
- [203] Warren T. Norman. 1963. Toward an adequate taxonomy of personality attributes: Replicated factor structure in peer nomination personality ratings. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology* 66, 6 (1963), 574.
- [204] Oded Nov and Chen Ye. 2008. Personality and technology acceptance: Personal innovativeness in IT, openness and resistance to change. In *Proceedings of the 41st Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. IEEE, 448–448.
- [205] Sam Nunn. 2005. Preventing the next terrorist attack: The theory and practice of homeland security information systems. *Journal of Homeland Security and Emergency Management* 2, 3 (2005).
- [206] Jon Oberlander and Alastair J. Gill. 2006. Language with character: A stratified corpus comparison of individual differences in e-mail communication. *Discourse Processes* 42, 3 (2006), 239–270.
- [207] Jon Oberlander and Scott Nowson. 2006. Whose thumb is it anyway?: Classifying author personality from weblog text. In *Proceedings of the COLING/ACL on Main Conference Poster Sessions*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 627–634.

- [208] Veronica Ong, Anneke D. S. Rahmanto, Derwin Suhartono, Aryo E. Nugroho, Esther W. Andangsari, Muhamad N. Suprayogi, et al. 2017. Personality prediction based on Twitter information in Bahasa Indonesia. In *Proceedings of the 2017 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems*. IEEE, 367–372.
- [209] Alvaro Ortigosa, Rosa M. Carro, and José Ignacio Quiroga. 2014. Predicting user personality by mining social interactions in Facebook. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* 80, 1 (2014), 57–71.
- [210] Julie E. Owen, Duhita Mahatmya, and Rebecca Carter. 2020. Dominance, influence, steadiness, and conscientiousness (DISC) assessment tool. In *Proceedings of the Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences*. Springer, 1186–1189.
- [211] Matthew J. Page, David Moher, Patrick M. Bossuyt, Isabelle Boutron, Tammy C. Hoffmann, Cynthia D. Mulrow, Larissa Shamseer, Jennifer M. Tetzlaff, Elie A. Akl, Sue E. Brennan, et al. 2021. PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372 (2021). arXiv:<https://www.bmj.com/content/372/bmj.n160.full.pdf> DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>
- [212] Maxwell Jerome Papurt. 1930. A study of the Woodworth Psychoneurotic Inventory with suggested revision. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology* 25, 3 (1930), 335.
- [213] Gregory Park, H. Andrew Schwartz, Johannes C. Eichstaedt, Margaret L. Kern, Michal Kosinski, David J. Stillwell, Lyle H. Ungar, and Martin E. P. Seligman. 2015. Automatic personality assessment through social media language. *Journal of personality and social psychology* 108, 6 (2015), 934.
- [214] Frank T. Passini and Warren T. Norman. 1966. A universal conception of personality structure? *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 4, 1 (1966), 44.
- [215] Dean Peabody and Boele De Raad. 2002. The substantive nature of psycholexical personality factors: A comparison across languages. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 83, 4 (2002), 983.
- [216] Dean Peabody and Lewis R. Goldberg. 1989. Some determinants of factor structures from personality-trait descriptors. *Journal of personality and Social Psychology* 57, 3 (1989), 552.
- [217] James W. Pennebaker, Martha E. Francis, and Roger J. Booth. 2001. Linguistic inquiry and word count: LIWC 2001. *Mahway: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates* 71, 2001 (2001), 2001.
- [218] James W. Pennebaker and Laura A. King. 1999. Linguistic styles: Language use as an individual difference. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 77, 6 (1999), 1296.
- [219] Heinrich Peters and Sandra C. Matz. 2024. Large language models can infer psychological dispositions of social media users. *PNAS Nexus* 3, 6 (2024), 231.
- [220] James G. Phillips, Sarah Butt, and Alex Blaszczynski. 2006. Personality and self-reported use of mobile phones for games. *CyberPsychology and Behavior* 9, 6 (2006), 753–758.
- [221] Fabio Pianesi, Nadia Mana, Alessandro Cappelletti, Bruno Lepri, and Massimo Zancanaro. 2008. Multimodal recognition of personality traits in social interactions. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces*. 53–60.
- [222] Fabio Pianesi, Massimo Zancanaro, Bruno Lepri, and Alessandro Cappelletti. 2007. A multimodal annotated corpus of consensus decision making meetings. *Language Resources and Evaluation* 41 (2007), 409–429.
- [223] Barbara Plank and Dirk Hovy. 2015. Personality traits on twitter - or - how to get 1,500 personality tests in a week. In *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Computational Approaches to Subjectivity, Sentiment and Social Media Analysis*.
- [224] Tim Polzehl, Sebastian Möller, and Florian Metze. 2010. Automatically assessing personality from speech. In *Proceedings of the 2010 IEEE 4th International Conference on Semantic Computing*. IEEE, 134–140.
- [225] Soujanya Poria, Alexandar Gelbukh, Basant Agarwal, Erik Cambria, and Newton Howard. 2013. Common sense knowledge based personality recognition from text. In *Advances in Soft Computing and Its Applications: 12th Mexican International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, MICAI 2013, Mexico City, Mexico, November 24-30, 2013, Proceedings, Part II 12*. Springer, 484–496.
- [226] Daniele Quercia, Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, and Jon Crowcroft. 2011. Our twitter profiles, our selves: Predicting personality with twitter. In *Proceedings of the 2011 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Privacy, Security, Risk and Trust and 2011 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Social Computing*. IEEE, 180–185.
- [227] Daniele Quercia, Renaud Lambiotte, David Stillwell, Michal Kosinski, and Jon Crowcroft. 2012. The personality of popular facebook users. In *Proceedings of the ACM 2012 Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work*. 955–964.
- [228] Muhannad Quwaider, Abdullah Alabed, and Rehab Duwairi. 2023. Shooter video games for personality prediction using five factor model traits and machine learning. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory* 122 (2023), 102665.
- [229] Colin Raffel, Noam Shazeer, Adam Roberts, Katherine Lee, Sharan Narang, Michael Matena, Yanqi Zhou, Wei Li, and Peter J. Liu. 2020. Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 21 (2020), 1–67.
- [230] Majid Ramezani, Mohammad-Reza Feizi-Derakhshi, and Mohammad-Ali Balafar. 2022. Knowledge graph-enabled text-based automatic personality prediction. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience* 2022, 1 (2022), 3732351.
- [231] Majid Ramezani, Mohammad-Reza Feizi-Derakhshi, and Mohammad-Ali Balafar. 2022. Text-based automatic personality prediction using KGrAt-Net: a knowledge graph attention network classifier. *Scientific Reports* 12, 1 (2022), 21453.

- [232] Majid Ramezani, Mohammad-Reza Feizi-Derakhshi, Mohammad-Ali Balafar, Meysam Asgari-Chenaghlu, Ali-Reza Feizi-Derakhshi, Narjes Nikzad-Khasmakhi, Mehrdad Ranjbar-Khadivi, Zoleikha Jahanbakhsh-Nagadeh, Elnaz Zafarani-Moattar, and Taymaz Akan. 2022. Automatic personality prediction: An enhanced method using ensemble modeling. *Neural Computing and Applications* 34, 21 (2022), 18369–18389.
- [233] Francisco Manuel Rangel Pardo, Fabio Celli, Paolo Rosso, Martin Potthast, Benno Stein, and Walter Daelemans. 2015. Overview of the 3rd author profiling task at PAN 2015. In *Proceedings of the CLEF 2015 Evaluation Labs and Workshop Working Notes Papers*. 1–8.
- [234] Brent W. Roberts and Hee J. Yoon. 2022. Personality psychology. *Annual Review of Psychology* 73 (2022), 489–516.
- [235] William Peter Robinson and Howard Giles. 1990. *Handbook of Language and Social Psychology*. Wiley Chichester, UK.
- [236] G. V. Rohit, K. Rakesh Bharadwaj, R. Hemanth, Bariti Pruthvi, and M. V. Manoj Kumar. 2020. Machine intelligence based personality prediction using social profile data. In *Proceedings of the 2020 3rd International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology*. IEEE, 1003–1008.
- [237] Alexandra Roshchina, John Cardiff, and Paolo Rosso. 2011. A comparative evaluation of personality estimation algorithms for the twin recommender system. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Search and Mining User-generated Contents*. 11–18.
- [238] Ethan Rublee, Vincent Rabaud, Kurt Konolige, and Gary Bradski. 2011. ORB: An efficient alternative to SIFT or SURF. In *Proceedings of the 2011 International Conference on Computer Vision*. IEEE, 2564–2571.
- [239] Gregorius Ryan, Pricillia Katarina, and Derwin Suhartono. 2023. Mbt personality prediction using machine learning and smote for balancing data based on statement sentences. *Information* 14, 4 (2023), 217.
- [240] Jitao Sang, Huaiwen Zhang, and Changsheng Xu. 2016. Visual BFI: An exploratory study for image-based personality test. In *Advances in Multimedia Information Processing-PCM 2016: 17th Pacific-Rim Conference on Multimedia, Xi'an, China, September 15-16, 2016, Proceedings, Part I*. Springer, 95–106.
- [241] Olga C. Santos. 2016. Emotions and personality in adaptive e-learning systems: an affective computing perspective. *Emotions and Personality in Personalized Services: Models, Evaluation and Applications* (2016), 263–285.
- [242] Chandrima Sarkar, Sumit Bhatia, Arvind Agarwal, and Juan Li. 2014. Feature analysis for computational personality recognition using youtube personality data set. In *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM Multi Media on Workshop on Computational Personality Recognition*. 11–14.
- [243] G. Nave D. J. Stillwell S. C. Matz, M. Kosinski. 2017. Psychological targeting as an effective approach to digital mass persuasion. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 114, 48 (2017), 12714–12719.
- [244] S. S. Vaid H. Peters G. M. Harari M. Cerf S. C. Matz, JD Teeny. 2024. The potential of generative AI for personalized persuasion at scale. *Scientific Reports* 14, 1 (2024), 4692.
- [245] Björn Schuller, Stefan Steidl, Anton Batliner, Elmar Nöth, Alessandro Vinciarelli, Felix Burkhardt, Rob Van Son, Felix Weninger, Florian Eyben, Tobias Bocklet, et al. 2012. The interspeech 2012 speaker trait challenge. In *Proceedings of the INTERSPEECH 2012*.
- [246] Andrew H. Schwartz, Johannes C. Eichstaedt, Margaret L. Kern, Lukasz Dziurzynski, Stephanie M. Ramones, Megha Agrawal, Achal Shah, Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, Martin E. P. Seligman, et al. 2013. Personality, gender, and age in the language of social media: The open-vocabulary approach. *PLoS one* 8, 9 (2013), 773–791.
- [247] Cristina Segalin, Fabio Celli, Luca Polonio, Michal Kosinski, David Stillwell, Nicu Sebe, Marco Cristani, and Bruno Lepri. 2017. What your facebook profile picture reveals about your personality. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 460–468.
- [248] Cristina Segalin, Dong Seon Cheng, and Marco Cristani. 2017. Social profiling through image understanding: Personality inference using convolutional neural networks. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding* 156 (2017), 34–50.
- [249] Crisitina Segalin, Alessandro Perina, Marco Cristani, and Alessandro Vinciarelli. 2016. The pictures we like are our image: continuous mapping of favorite pictures into self-assessed and attributed personality traits. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 8, 2 (2016), 268–285.
- [250] Doaa Shawky and Ashraf Badawi. 2019. Towards a personalized learning experience using reinforcement learning. *Machine Learning Paradigms: Theory and Application* (2019), 169–187.
- [251] Siyang Song, Shashank Jaiswal, Enrique Sanchez, Georgios Tzimiropoulos, Linlin Shen, and Michel Valstar. 2021. Self-supervised learning of person-specific facial dynamics for automatic personality recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 14, 1 (2021), 178–195.
- [252] Alireza Souri, Shafiqeh Hosseinpour, and Amir Masoud Rahmani. 2018. Personality classification based on profiles of social networks' users and the five-factor model of personality. *Human-Centric Computing and Information Sciences* 8, 1 (2018), 24.
- [253] Ruchir Srivastava, Jiashi Feng, Sujoy Roy, Shuicheng Yan, and Terence Sim. 2012. Don't ask me what I'm like, just watch and listen. In *Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 329–338.
- [254] Jacopo Staiano, Bruno Lepri, Nadav Aharoni, Fabio Pianesi, Nicu Sebe, and Alex Pentland. 2012. Friends don't lie: Inferring personality traits from social network structure. In *Proceedings of the 2012 ACM Conference on Ubiquitous Computing*. ACM, 321–330.

- [255] Jacopo Staiano, Bruno Lepri, Ramanathan Subramanian, Nicu Sebe, and Fabio Pianesi. 2011. Automatic modeling of personality states in small group interactions. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. ACM, 989–992.
- [256] Ramanathan Subramanian, Yan Yan, Jacopo Staiano, Oswald Lanz, and Nicu Sebe. 2013. On the relationship between head pose, social attention and personality prediction for unstructured and dynamic group interactions. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM on International Conference on Multimodal Interaction*. 3–10.
- [257] Tom Sühr, Florian E. Dorner, Samira Samadi, and Augustin Kelava. 2025. Challenging the validity of personality tests for large language models. In *Proceedings of the 2025 Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization*. 74–81.
- [258] Chanchal Suman, Sriparna Saha, Aditya Gupta, Saurabh Kumar Pandey, and Pushpak Bhattacharyya. 2022. A multi-modal personality prediction system. *Knowledge-Based Systems* 236 (2022), 107715.
- [259] Chris Sumner, Alison Byers, Rachel Boochever, and Gregory J. Park. 2012. Predicting dark triad personality traits from twitter usage and a linguistic analysis of tweets. In *Proceedings of the 2012 11th International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications*. IEEE, 386–393.
- [260] Guangzhi Sun, Xiao Zhan, and Jose Such. 2024. Building better ai agents: A provocation on the utilisation of persona in llm-based conversational agents. In *Proceedings of the 6th ACM Conference on Conversational User Interfaces*. 1–6.
- [261] Shlomo Argamon Sushant, Shlomo Argamon, Sushant Dhawle, and James W. Pennebaker. 2005. Lexical predictors of personality type. In *Proceedings of the Joint Annual Meeting of the Interface and the Classification Society of North America*. 1–16.
- [262] Ludovic Terren Ludovic Terren and Rosa Borge-Bravo Rosa Borge-Bravo. 2021. Echo chambers on social media: A systematic review of the literature. *Review of Communication Research* 9 (2021).
- [263] Menasha Thilakararatne, Ruvan Weerasinghe, and Sujana Perera. 2016. Knowledge-driven approach to predict personality traits by leveraging social media data. In *Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Web Intelligence*. IEEE, 288–295.
- [264] Marko Tkalcic, Matevz Kunaver, Andrej Košir, and Jurij Tasic. 2011. Addressing the new user problem with a personality based user similarity measure. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Decision Making and Recommendation Acceptance Issues in Recommender Systems*. 106–111.
- [265] Marc Tomlinson, David Hinote, and David Bracewell. 2013. Predicting conscientiousness through semantic analysis of facebook posts. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 31–34.
- [266] Natkamon Tovanich, Simone Centellegher, Nacéra Bennacer Seghouani, Joe Gladstone, Sandra Matz, and Bruno Lepri. 2021. Inferring psychological traits from spending categories and dynamic consumption patterns. *EPJ Data Science* 10, 1 (2021), 24.
- [267] Timothy J. Trull and David C. Geary. 1997. Comparison of the big-five factor structure across samples of Chinese and American adults. *Journal of Personality Assessment* 69, 2 (1997), 324–341.
- [268] Simon Tucker and Steve Whittaker. 2005. Accessing multimodal meeting data: Systems, problems and possibilities. In *Machine Learning for Multimodal Interaction: 1st International Workshop, MLMI 2004, Martigny, Switzerland, June 21–23, 2004, Revised Selected Papers 1*. Springer, 1–11.
- [269] Simine Vazire. 2010. Who knows what about a person? The self–other knowledge asymmetry (SOKA) model. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 98, 2 (2010), 281.
- [270] Carles Ventura, David Masip, and Agata Lapedriza. 2017. Interpreting cnn models for apparent personality trait regression. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*. 55–63.
- [271] Ben Verhoeven, Walter Daelemans, and Tom De Smedt. 2013. Ensemble methods for personality recognition. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 35–38.
- [272] Alessandro Vinciarelli and Gelareh Mohammadi. 2014. A survey of personality computing. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 5, 3 (2014), 273–291.
- [273] Peng Wang, Meng Yan, Xiangping Zhan, Mei Tian, Yingdong Si, Yu Sun, Longzhen Jiao, and Xiaojie Wu. 2021. Predicting self-reported proactive personality classification with Weibo text and short answer text. *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), 77203–77211.
- [274] Weichen Wang, Gabriella M. Harari, Rui Wang, Sandrine R. Müller, Shayan Mirjafari, Kizito Masaba, and Andrew T. Campbell. 2018. Sensing behavioral change over time: Using within-person variability features from mobile sensing to predict personality traits. *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 2, 3 (2018), 1–21.
- [275] Xintao Wang, Yunze Xiao, Jen-tse Huang, Siyu Yuan, Rui Xu, Haoran Guo, Quan Tu, Yaying Fei, Ziang Leng, Wei Wang, et al. 2024. InCharacter: Evaluating personality fidelity in role-playing agents through psychological interviews. In *Proceedings of the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. Lun-Wei Ku, Andre Martins, and Vivek Srikumar (Eds.), Association for Computational Linguistics, Bangkok, Thailand, 1840–1873.

- [276] Yilei Wang, Jiabao Zhao, Deniz S. Ones, Liang He, and Xin Xu. 2025. Evaluating the ability of large language models to emulate personality. *Scientific Reports* 15, 1 (2025), 519.
- [277] Zhiyuan Wen, Jiannong Cao, Yu Yang, Haoli Wang, Ruosong Yang, and Shuaiqi Liu. 2023. DesPrompt: Personality-descriptive prompt tuning for few-shot personality recognition. *Information Processing and Management* 60, 5 (2023), 103422.
- [278] David William and Derwin Suhartono. 2021. Text-based depression detection on social media posts: A systematic literature review. *Procedia Computer Science* 179 (2021), 582–589.
- [279] Michael Wilson. 1988. MRC psycholinguistic database: Machine-usable dictionary, version 2.00. *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, and Computers* 20, 1 (1988), 6–10.
- [280] Bernhard Wolf. 2005. Brunswik’s original lens model. *University of Landau, Germany* 9 (2005), 1–9.
- [281] William R. Wright and David N. Chin. 2014. Personality profiling from text: introducing part-of-speech N-grams. In *User Modeling, Adaptation, and Personalization: 22nd International Conference, UMAP 2014, Aalborg, Denmark, July 7–11, 2014. Proceedings* 22. Springer, 243–253.
- [282] Cao Xiao, David Mandell Freeman, and Theodore Hwa. 2015. Detecting clusters of fake accounts in online social networks. In *Proceedings of the 8th ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security*. 91–101.
- [283] Xiaoyu Xiong, Maurizio Filippone, and Alessandro Vinciarelli. 2016. Looking good with Flickr faves: Gaussian processes for finding difference makers in personality impressions. In *Proceedings of the 24th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 412–415.
- [284] Jia Xu, Weijian Tian, Guoyun Lv, Shiya Liu, and Yangyu Fan. 2021. Prediction of the big five personality traits using static facial images of college students with different academic backgrounds. *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), 76822–76832.
- [285] Di Xue, Zheng Hong, Shize Guo, Liang Gao, Lifa Wu, Jinghua Zheng, and Nan Zhao. 2017. Personality recognition on social media with label distribution learning. *IEEE Access* 5 (2017), 13478–13488.
- [286] Di Xue, Lifa Wu, Zheng Hong, Shize Guo, Liang Gao, Zhiyong Wu, Xiaofeng Zhong, and Jianshan Sun. 2018. Deep learning-based personality recognition from text posts of online social networks. *Applied Intelligence* 48 (2018), 4232–4246.
- [287] Xia Xue, Jun Feng, and Xia Sun. 2021. Semantic-enhanced sequential modeling for personality trait recognition from texts. *Applied Intelligence* (2021), 1–13.
- [288] C. Y. Yaakub, N. Sulaiman, and C. W. Kim. 2010. A study on personality identification using game based theory. In *Proceedings of the 2010 2nd International Conference on Computer Technology and Development*. IEEE, 732–734.
- [289] Kosuke Yamada, Ryohei Sasano, and Koichi Takeda. 2019. Incorporating textual information on user behavior for personality prediction. In *Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Student Research Workshop*. 177–182.
- [290] Hsin-Chang Yang and Zi-Rui Huang. 2019. Mining personality traits from social messages for game recommender systems. *Knowledge-Based Systems* 165 (2019), 157–168.
- [291] Kai Yang, Hui Yuan, and Raymond Y. K. Lau. 2022. PsyCredit: An interpretable deep learning-based credit assessment approach facilitated by psychometric natural language processing. *Expert Systems with Applications* 198 (2022), 116847.
- [292] Wen Yeye, Chen Deyuan, Li Baobin, Wang Xiaoyang, Liu Xiaoqian, and Zhu Tingshao. 2020. Predicting personality based on self-introduction video. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 53, 5 (2020), 452–457.
- [293] Wu Youyou, Michal Kosinski, and David Stillwell. 2015. Computer-based personality judgments are more accurate than those made by humans. *PNAS* 112, 4 (2015), 1036–1040.
- [294] Jianguo Yu and Konstantin Markov. 2017. Deep learning based personality recognition from facebook status updates. In *Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE 8th International Conference on Awareness Science and Technology*. IEEE, 383–387.
- [295] Brahim Zarouali, Tom Dobber, Guy De Pauw, and Claes de Vreese. 2022. Using a personality-profiling algorithm to investigate political microtargeting: assessing the persuasion effects of personality-tailored ads on social media. *Communication Research* 49, 8 (2022), 1066–1091.
- [296] Gloria Zen, Bruno Lepri, Elisa Ricci, and Oswald Lanz. 2010. Space speaks: Towards socially and personality aware visual surveillance. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM International Workshop on Multimodal Pervasive Video Analysis*. 37–42.
- [297] Shanyang Zhao, Sherri Grasmuck, and Jason Martin. 2008. Identity construction on facebook: Digital empowerment in anchored relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior* 24, 5 (2008), 1816–1836.
- [298] Lin Zhou and Wenjun An. 2022. Data classification of mental health and personality evaluation based on network deep learning. *Mobile Information Systems* 2022, 1 (2022), 9251598.
- [299] Michelle X. Zhou, Gloria Mark, Jingyi Li, and Huahai Yang. 2019. Trusting virtual agents: The effect of personality. *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems* 9, 2-3 (2019), 1–36.

Received 3 March 2025; revised 14 January 2026; accepted 24 March 2026